

REPORT:

A2.4.4: technical report describing the design, fabrication, and calibration process of the transfer standards

Workpackage 2

This report was written as part of activity A2.4.4 from the EMPIR Establishing Metrology Standards in Microfluidic Devices (MFMET) project. The three-year European project commenced on 1st June 2021 and focused on providing a generic methodology of accurate measurement of a particular quantity in a microfluidic device by utilising standardised methods and reference documents, e.g. VIM & GUM. For more details about this project, please visit www.mfmet.eu

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1. Scope

The objective of this document is to present the results of the tests on the golden standard samples, both glass and polymer standards. Additionally, the design and fabrication of the standards will be explained in detail. The tests protocols have been defined in A2.4.3 and various members of the project conducted these tests, according to their testing capabilities.

Activity number	Activity description	Partners (lead in bold)
A2.4.4 M35	Using input from A2.4.1-A2.4.3, IMTAG with support from CETIAT, LNE and microfluidic will produce a technical report describing the design, fabrication, and calibration process of the transfer standards and share this report in the relevant standardisation group such as CEN/TC332/WG7 and/or ISO/TC48/WG3.	IMTAG , CETIAT, LNE, microfluidic

The transfer standards – microfluidic chips will be used as reference objects to ensure traceability, comparability, and validity of the microfluidics manufacturers and users’ measurement and testing capabilities. They will be characterized at National Metrology Institutes with best available accuracies for flow, flow resistivity, volume, dimensions, roughness and surface energy. They are designed to cover the typical microfluidics needs for the pre-cited quantities.

The two most commonly used base materials for microfluidic chips are glass and polymer. For each type of transfer standard, different connections and assemblies were used.

In the following, the design and fabrication of the transfer standards made of glass and polymer are explained in detail.

2. Glass transfer standards

2.1. Fabrication and design of the transfer standards made of glass

D236[®] bio wafers from SCHOTT were used in the manufacturing process of the glass chips. This borosilicate glass D236[®] bio exhibits a very low intrinsic autofluorescence across the UV to NIR spectrum and is therefore often used in microfluidic applications for fluorescence measurements. Processes similar to those used in the semiconductor industry are used to convert a glass substrate into a microfluidic device. This method also allows to fabricate various designs spread on the same wafer, exhibiting though one specific channel depth. Channels in glass were isotropically wet etched using hydrofluoric acid-based etching solutions. Access holes in glass are generated by laser assisted glass etching, which uses a focused laser beam to modify the glass substrate in the shape of the access

holes. A chemical solution is applied to selectively etch along these modifications, which allows the creation of vertically shaped walls for the access holes. The bonding of two glass wafers to form a closed microfluidic device was done by fusion bonding. For this method the two substrates are brought into contact and subsequently, a heat treatment was applied for a long duration, which facilitated the glass-to-glass fusion process. Separating the whole wafer package into individual devices was done via laser dicing.

For the glass transfer standards, two substrates (both wafers made of D236[®] bio with a diameter of Ø200 mm and a thickness of 1 mm) were processed with different channel and access hole structures. As shown in Figure 1, the TOP substrate contained a leakage channel(s) and a logo (“IMT for MFMET”). Both structures were etched isotropically with a hydrofluoric acid-based etching solution to a depth of 2 µm and a width of 150 µm. The BOTTOM substrate contained a deeper (100 µm) and wider (1 mm) channel(s). Again, the length of these channels in the BOTTOM substrate varied for each design and in one design itself. All access holes exhibited a diameter of Ø800 µm. Their position is according to ISO 22916 [1]. The chip dimensions were 15 mm x 45 mm, which was also according to the ISO 22916. Table 1 shows the technical specification of the microfluidic devices. In certain designs, the length of the channels may vary.

Schematic view from the side

Figure 1: Schematic view of the transfer standard glass chip.

Table 1: Technical specification for the transfer standards made of glass.

Description of the parameter	Value	Tolerance	Comment
Thickness of TOP	1.0 mm	± 0.025 mm	D236 [®] bio
Depth of leakage channel	2.0 µm	± 0.5 µm	
Width of leakage channel	150 µm	± 5.0 µm	
Thickness of BOTTOM	1.0 mm	± 0.025 mm	D236 [®] bio
Depth of leakage channel	100.0 µm	± 5.0 µm	
Width of leakage channel	1.0 mm	± 26.0 µm	
Access holes	Ø 0.8 mm	± 0.1 mm	

During the design of the transfer standards, the following objectives were considered [2]:

1. Compare the leakage rate measurement with air (preferred industrial test method) with liquid leakage rate (in microfluidic application);
2. Enable very low flows for flow rate measurements.

Therefore, several very small channels (here called leakage channels) with common inlet port and separate outlet ports should be considered. One should be able to close or open such ports individually.

The leakage channel allows for a liquid flow rate of 10 nL/min minimum with an inlet pressure of 100 mbar to 2 bar. The set of 8 transfer standards designs allows to test separately simple microfluidic geometries and their combinations, representing typical fluidic configurations encountered by microfluidic end users. The design process is driven in accordance with existing ISO standards (such as ISO 22916 for port pitch and dimensions) and MFMET consortium technical recommendations. In the following, the 8 designs are described separately for their appearance and purpose (green: BOTTOM structure, blue: TOP structure, orange: access holes in BOTTOM substrate):

2.1.1. Design 1

Single measurement channel (150 μm width, 2 μm depth, 5 mm length) with 2 access channels (1 mm width, 100 μm depth, 40 mm length) and identical calibration channel.

Specific purpose: test simplest flow resistivity measurement capability.

2.1.2. Design 2

Two single measurement channels in parallel (150 μm width, 2 μm depth, 5 mm length each) with 2 access channels (1 mm width, 100 μm depth, 40 mm length) and identical calibration channel.

Specific purpose: test flow resistivity combination measurement capability.

2.1.3. Design 3

Two single measurement channels in series with a U-bend (150 μm width, 2 μm depth, 10 mm length) with 2 access channels (1 mm width, 100 μm depth, 40 mm length) and identical calibration channel. Specific purpose: test flow resistivity measurement capability with additional resistivity component (U-bend).

2.1.4. Design 4

Two single measurement channels in series with a serpentine geometry (150 μm width, 2 μm depth, 10 mm length) with 2 access channels (1 mm width, 100 μm depth, 40 mm length) and identical calibration channel.

Specific purpose: test flow resistivity measurement capability with additional resistivity component (serpentine).

2.1.5. Design 5

Three measurement channels 1, 2 and 3 times of a single channel length (150 μm width, 2 μm depth, 5, 10 and 15 mm length) with 2 access channels (1 mm width, 100 μm depth, 40 mm length) and identical calibration channel.

Specific purpose: test flow resistivity measurement capability with additional resistivity component (additivity of single lengths resistivity).

2.1.6. Design 6

Single measurement channel (150 μm width, 2 μm depth, 5 mm length) with 1 access channel (1 mm width, 100 μm depth, 40 mm length) and identical calibration channel.

Specific purpose: test leakage-like flow resistivity measurement capability.

2.1.7. Design 7

Single measurement channel with serpentine geometry (150 μm width, 2 μm depth, 10 mm length) with 1 access channel (1 mm width, 100 μm depth, 40 mm length) and identical calibration channel.

Specific purpose: test leakage-like flow resistivity measurement capability with additional resistivity component (serpentine).

2.1.8. Design 8

Four measurement channels (150 μm width, 2 μm depth, 7.46 mm and 13.26 mm length on both sides) with 1 access channel (1 mm width, 100 μm depth, 40 mm length) and identical calibration channel.

Specific purpose: test flow resistivity measurement capability with additional resistivity components (angle and flow direction).

2.2. Connectors for the transfer standards made of glass

For the interfacing to the glass chips, standardized connectors are used, which enable top-down connections as well as side connections, see Figure 2 for the definitions of top and side definitions.

Figure 2: Schematics showing definitions of top, side and edge (left); top connection (middle) and side connection (right).

The connectors are designed for a 15 mm wide (glass) chip with a fluidic port on a 3 mm pitch providing a set of 4 fluidic connections in a row with 3 mm spacing according to ISO 22916 (Table 1), they were specifically constructed for these chips. The connector is milled in PEEK (polyetheretherketon) material, a high-performance polymer. The interface uses perfluoroelastomer ferrules to seal on the flat service of the glass chip. Typically, PTFE tubing is used as it provides flexible and resistant tubing to connect to external instrumentation. This interface connector needs to be clamped onto the glass chip applying sealing pressure between the ferrules and the glass surface. Clamping is done by screwing the connector onto a support frame that also supports the glass chip. The connector enables a fast, easy and robust connection to the glass chips. An illustration of the connector with a supporting frame is represented in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Schematics showing definitions of top, side and edge (left); top connection (middle) and side connection (right) for the glass chip.

2.3. Results of the experiments conducted in A2.4.3

The results of the measurements performed with the glass transfer standards are presented in the following sub-sections. See also section 4 about the challenges encountered during these measurements.

2.3.1. Dimensions

2.3.1.1. LNE

The batch of transfer standards to be measured by optical microscopy consists of 8 different designs. 3 series were produced for each design except for the designs 6&7 (2 series) and 8 (only 1).

2.3.1.1.1. Instruments

Two microscopes (Figure 4) were used depending on the dimensional range of the patterns to be measured. The Table 2 details the information about these two instruments including the reference structures (see Figure 5) involved in the calibration process. Different reference structure (test pattern) allows us to calibrate the instrument. The calibration procedure makes measurements traceable by creating a link between measurement results and SI units. Uncertainties linked to calibration are included in the Table 2.

Table 2: information about the both instruments used for dimensional measurements

Instrument	reference	range	Lens	calibration	Uncertainty linked to calibration
Optical Microscope	Olympus BX53M	< 10 000 μm	X 1,5 X 5 X15	Test pattern	0.1 %
Stereo Binocular Microscope	Leica wild M3Z	> 10 000 μm	X 2,56	Test pattern	2 %

Figure 4: a) Optical Microscope Olympus used for measuring width and hole diameters of the channel and leakage channel; b) Stereo Binocular Microscope Leica for the channel length measurements.

Figure 5: standards used for the calibration process : a) calibration test pattern for Olympus BX53M and b) calibration test pattern for stereo binocular Leica.

2.3.1.1.2. Measurements

Glass transfer standards involved in the project are microfluidic devices consisting of one or several main channels. Some of them are connected to one or several leakage channels. The objective of this protocol is to determine the following dimensional parameters:

- The width and length of the main and leakage channels.
- The diameter of the holes located at the ends of each main channel or leakage channel used as connectors.

Most of channels are linear but designs 3, 4, 7 and 8 present channels with curves (U, L or more complex shapes). Specific analysis tools were used to measure these non-linear channels.

All tested designs are reported in Figure 3 with the various patterns to be characterized.

Figure 6: Different designs of the 8 reference standards with the identification of each patterns to be measured.

The width of main and leakage channels, the length of leakage channels and the diameters of the hole for connection have been measured with Olympus microscope (X10 or X5). Images were analysed with the software Olympus Stream Essentials 2.3.3 (build 17023). This software includes a special function capable of merging all the focal planes into a single image. This tool allows us to identify the main focal plan on all images as shown in the Figure 7. We have taken the largest dimension to be the width of the channels (red arrows). Regarding the hole measurement, a specific tool with circular shape was used. In this case, the main focal plan is quite difficult to identify. A large number of very close focal planes are observed. This is probably due to the hole-drilling phase during the manufacturing process of microfluidic devices.

Each measurement is repeated three times at different points in the channels and holes. A standard deviation, σ_r , is then calculated. σ_r therefore represents both the repeatability of the measurement and the inhomogeneity of the patterns. Each measurement is associated with an uncertainty, σ , calculated as the following quadratic sum:

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\sigma_r^2 + \sigma_c^2}$$

σ_c denotes the uncertainty linked to calibration.

Figure 7: Example of images obtained after merging and highlighting the main focal plans.
a) middle of the channel 2; b) hole 2 of the channel 3; c) middle of the leakage channel and d) end of the leakage channel.

Figure 8: examples of how to use the tools “distance between two points” and “customised path” on a) leakage bottom right and top right of the design 8 and b) the leakage of the design 4.

2.3.1.1.3. Data

In the following tables, the data in the yellow boxes correspond to measurements taken with the binocular microscope. The length measurements below are stated in micro-meters.

Measurement results obtained on the three series of the design 01:

Design01 - serie 01	Hole 01		Hole 02		width		Length	
	Diam.	σ	Diam.	σ	Meas.	σ	Meas.	σ
Channel 01	813,14	11,37	829,02	1,61	998,10	1,78	40121,78	802
Channel 02	822,85	3,55	821,10	0,82	1001,59	2,93	40136,43	803
Channel 03	822,20	3,93	825,52	0,17	999,26	1,35	40078,11	802
Leakage Channel					152,60	0,35	6002,60	6

Design01 - serie 02	Hole 01		Hole 02		width		Length	
	Diam.	σ	Diam.	σ	Meas.	σ	Meas.	σ
Channel 01	802,07	9,27	812,18	7,70	1003,47	1,44	39786,32	796
Channel 02	805,23	9,44	805,64	4,38	1003,62	3,08	39786,50	796
Channel 03	804,25	14,37	810,86	1,41	1004,21	3,24	39771,98	795
Leakage Channel					153,02	4,07	6002,60	6

Design01 - serie 03	Hole 01		Hole 02		width		Length	
	Diam.	σ	Diam.	σ	Meas.	σ	Meas.	σ
Channel 01	820,95	3,51	826,10	7,96	997,38	0,89	39289,01	786
Channel 02	825,36	1,18	820,13	9,68	999,72	5,49	39289,04	786
Channel 03	819,14	2,10	822,47	5,12	997,58	0,89	39289,12	786
Leakage Channel					153,40	1,68	6002,60	6

Measurement results obtained on the three series of the design 02:

Design02 - serie 01	Hole 01		Hole 02		width		Length	
	Diam.	σ	Diam.	σ	Meas.	σ	Meas.	σ
Channel 01	826,94	0,12	828,32	3,57	996,94	2,42	39877,08	798
Channel 02	822,42	2,98	831,55	12,83	1001,21	2,93	39865,55	797
Channel 03	819,50	16,05	821,95	3,05	997,33	3,07	39865,53	797
L Leakage Channel					152,06	0,67	6009,63	6
R Leakage Channel					152,06	0,67	6009,60	6

Design02 - serie 02	Hole 01		Hole 02		width		Length	
	Diam.	σ	Diam.	σ	Meas.	σ	Meas.	σ
Channel 01	815,46	7,49	821,41	4,67	997,00	0,89	39318,21	786
Channel 02	817,44	11,14	819,02	10,72	996,61	1,00	39303,58	786
Channel 03	823,39	17,58	820,22	13,39	997,39	1,69	39288,95	786
L Leakage Channel					153,01	2,10	6013,47	6
R Leakage Channel					153,40	2,20	6018,13	6

Design02 - serie 03	Hole 01		Hole 02		width		Length	
	Diam.	σ	Diam.	σ	Meas.	σ	Meas.	σ
Channel 01	810,74	6,54	823,15	4,71	1000,87	1,21	39464,45	789
Channel 02	814,65	5,85	821,57	4,59	1000,10	3,02	39405,93	788
Channel 03	818,38	9,65	810,08	14,19	1000,49	1,34	39391,55	788
L Leakage Channel					152,24	0,33	6018,14	6
R Leakage Channel					151,66	0,67	6022,82	6

Measurement results obtained on the three series of the design 03:

Design03 - serie 01	Hole 01		Hole 02		width		Length	
	Diam.	σ	Diam.	σ	Meas.	σ	Meas.	σ
Channel 01	829,00	9,03	817,92	17,12	999,42	1,24	39873,56	797
Channel 02			832,62	13,40	999,37	1,97	32056,72	641
Channel 03			832,62	11,11	996,94	1,34	50970,5	1019
U Leakage Channel					153,22	0,67	10949,00	219

Design03 - serie 02	Hole 01		Hole 02		width		Length	
	Diam.	σ	Diam.	σ	Meas.	σ	Meas.	σ
Channel 01	810,25	2,13	813,94	10,03	999,52	0,58	39669,10	793
Channel 02			824,56	2,91	1000,87	2,42	31881,34	638
Channel 03			819,08	19,24	996,59	1,34	50945,00	1019
U Leakage Channel					153,79	1,21	11003,00	220

Design03 - serie 03	Hole 01		Hole 02		width		Length	
	Diam.	σ	Diam.	σ	Meas.	σ	Meas.	σ
Channel 01	823,21	11,25	815,11	5,15	1000,49	0,67	39844,19	797
Channel 02			816,26	2,97	999,32	1,87	32012,73	640
Channel 03			813,60	0,83	1001,07	1,00	51075,00	1021
U Leakage Channel					151,07	0,34	10995,00	220

Measurement results obtained on the three series of the design 04:

Design04 - serie 01	Hole 01		Hole 02		width		Length	
	Diam.	σ	Diam.	σ	Meas.	σ	Meas.	σ
Channel 01	808,13	12,46	805,34	29,77	999,64	1,19	39581,55	792
Channel 02	816,76	9,38	828,12	1,83	998,88	1,34	39581,70	792
Channel 03	815,57	6,41	821,38	5,80	999,66	2,34	39581,95	792
Leakage Channel					151,29	1,17	10852,00	217

Design04 - serie 02	Hole 01		Hole 02		width		Length	
	Diam.	σ	Diam.	σ	Meas.	σ	Meas.	σ
Channel 01	808,72	6,00	811,85	2,81	998,93	1,75	40078,16	802
Channel 02	812,47	2,33	814,20	0,23	998,94	0,59	40092,77	802
Channel 03	811,57	0,25	814,26	2,54	998,74	1,87	40093,07	802
Leakage Channel					150,88	0,89	10890,00	218

Design04 - serie 03	Hole 01		Hole 02		width		Length	
	Diam.	σ	Diam.	σ	Meas.	σ	Meas.	σ
Channel 01	812,39	1,97	812,34	0,40	999,32	1,21	39566,62	791
Channel 02	810,35	1,95	813,74	0,15	999,13	1,78	39566,65	791
Channel 03	810,66	3,36	813,91	0,40	999,71	1,78	39552,16	791
Leakage Channel					151,07	0,68	10980,00	220

Measurement results obtained on the three series of the design 05:

Design05 - serie 01	Hole 01		Hole 02		width		Length	
	Diam.	σ	Diam.	σ	Meas.	σ	Meas.	σ
Channel 01	813,64	15,92	802,89	13,84	996,94	2,68	39581,17	792
Channel 02	810,21	17,56	818,96	14,92	995,00	2,33	12258,62	245
							R 12404,73	248
Channel 03	818,54	9,81	812,46	19,75	997,32	4,20	14742,49	295
							R 14859,37	297
Channel 04	810,07	14,72	813,21	13,60	995,38	1,35	17270,19	345
							R 17328,64	347
Leakage Channel 02					153,23	2,42	16158,90	16
Leakage Channel 03					153,61	0,33	11053,48	11
Leakage Channel 04					152,45	2,43	6028,32	6

Design05 - serie 02	Hole 01		Hole 02		width		Length	
	Diam.	σ	Diam.	σ	Meas.	σ	Meas.	σ
Channel 01	813,99	6,07	812,51	3,97	997,77	2,10	39727,32	795
Channel 02	802,25	1,57	810,69	0,81	999,91	2,35	12317,14	246
							R 12448,56	249
Channel 03	807,11	1,67	812,54	3,27	999,13	1,35	14786,33	296
							R 14947,07	299
Channel 04	806,38	2,01	811,25	0,81	1000,31	2,38	17270,19	345
							R 17401,69	348
Leakage Channel 02					153,01	0,58	16123,50	16
Leakage Channel 03					152,04	0,33	11042,73	11
Leakage Channel 04					152,62	0,67	6008,82	6

Design05 serie 03	Hole 01		Hole 02		width		Length	
	Diam.	σ	Diam.	σ	Meas.	σ	Meas.	σ
Channel 01	811,24	1,29	813,17	2,48	997,42	1,49	39362,01	787
Channel 02	814,07	0,28	813,32	1,10	996,41	1,46	12258,63	245
							R 12331,71	247
Channel 03	812,81	1,25	812,83	0,81	997,77	3,54	14684,05	294
							R 14771,72	295
Channel 04	809,63	1,54	810,60	2,48	999,71	3,21	17094,86	342
							R 17240,99	345
Leakage Channel 02					151,07	0,68	16137,40	16
Leakage Channel 03					151,66	0,33	11051,98	11
Leakage Channel 04					151,07	0,68	6022,81	6

Measurement results obtained on the two series of the design 06:

Design06 - serie 01	Hole 01		Hole 02		width		Length	
	Diam.	σ	Diam.	σ	Meas.	σ	Meas.	σ
Channel 01	798,04	6,98	822,18	9,62	995,83	2,05	39508,72	790
Channel 02	815,29	12,99	821,93	9,92	997,97	2,01	39508,89	790
Leakage Channel	812,46	1,98			151,85	0,67	6018,13	6

Design06 - serie 02	Hole 01		Hole 02		width		Length	
	Diam.	σ	Diam.	σ	Meas.	σ	Meas.	σ
Channel 01	814,95	0,81	816,33	3,37	996,30	0,90	39829,72	797
Channel 02	812,70	0,81	813,85	3,43	997,82	3,05	39829,68	797
Leakage Channel	810,82	1,26			150,88	1,21	6022,82	6

Measurement results obtained on the two series of the design 07:

Design07 - serie 01	Hole 01		Hole 02		width		Length	
	Diam.	σ	Diam.	σ	Meas.	σ	Meas.	σ
Channel 01	811,56	10,63	822,37	5,11	996,80	1,21	40063,33	801
Channel 02	816,76	11,62	821,93	9,92	997,97	1,46	40077,95	802
Leakage Channel	820,53	6,88			151,85	1,16	10930,00	219

Design07 - serie 02	Hole 01		Hole 02		width		Length	
	Diam.	σ	Diam.	σ	Meas.	σ	Meas.	σ
Channel 01	812,75	3,54	813,54	1,60	996,50	2,73	39727,32	795
Channel 02	811,49	3,50	812,65	2,33	994,47	3,87	39742,02	795
Leakage Channel	810,59	1,75			151,46	0,89	10900,00	218

Measurement results obtained on the design 08:

Design08	Hole 01		Hole 02		width		Length	
	Diam.	σ	Diam.	σ	Meas.	σ	Meas.	σ
Channel 01	816,50	6,68	821,99	1,17	996,80	1,78	39741,89	795
Bottom L Leakage channel	825,30	3,71			153,01	0,58	17470	349
Bottom R Leakage	825,09	6,32			155,15	0,33	17460	349
Top L Leakage	819,58	12,12			152,49	1,19	8583,83	9
Top RLeakage	822,23	10,57			153,45	1,80	8540,75	9

2.3.1.1. CEA

2.3.1.1.1. Instrument

Optical profilometry is a method that uses light instead of a physical probe to characterize geometries. This allows non-destructive measurements without the need to get in direct contact with the object. Because of its light-based nature, it is particularly suitable for measurements within transparent substrates. A SmartScope ZIP®250 (with its accompanying software ZONE3© (both from Optical Gaging Products (OGP) part of Quality Vision International (QVI), NY, USA) was used to perform measurements of the internal geometries. Table 3 gives details of the instrument. The setup is shown in Figure 9.

Table 3: Specifications of the instrument used for dimension measurements.

Instrument	Range	Lens	Lighting	Calibration	Uncertainty linked to calibration
OGP SmartScope ZIP®250	> 1 μm	x1 x2	Substage LED profile Coaxial LED surface SmartRing™ LED ring light	Annual calibration report by OGP	In plane (XY): $\pm 2 \mu\text{m} + 4L/1000$ Vertically (Z): $\pm 2.5 \mu\text{m} + 5L/1000$ In-image: < 1 μm

Figure 9: Optical profilometer OGP SmartScope ZIP®250

2.3.1.1.2. Measurements

It followed the same protocol used by LNE as presented in 2.3.1.1.2, see Figure 6 for the references of the features inside the chips.

2.3.1.1.3. Data

The length measurements below are stated in micro-meters.

Measurement results obtained on the three series of the design 01:

Design 01 - series 01	Hole 01		Hole 02		Width		Depth		Length	
	Diam.	u	Diam.	u	Meas.	u	Meas.	u	Meas.	u
Channel 01	804,9	1,0	809,8	1,5	991,3	1,0	1 055,0	8,2	39 805,9	161,2
Channel 02	804,9	1,0	841,0	3,8	992,1	1,0	1 050,7	8,3	39 824,5	161,3
Channel 03	828,7	1,0	803,0	2,5	992,4	1,0	1 050,1	8,1	39 819,1	161,3
Leakage Channel					143,0	1,1	N/A	N/A	5 998,9	26,0

Design 01 - series 02	Hole 01		Hole 02		Width		Depth		Length	
	Diam.	u	Diam.	u	Meas.	u	Meas.	u	Meas.	u
Channel 01	804,8	7,3	813,1	1,8	994,7	1,1	1 059,3	7,8	39 805,1	161,6
Channel 02	806,4	2,8	839,6	2,3	993,5	1,0	1 054,9	7,9	39 974,4	313,5
Channel 03	830,2	2,9	803,9	11,0	993,3	1,0	1 055,1	8,0	39 816,6	161,5
Leakage Channel					143,2	1,0	N/A	N/A	5 999,0	26,0

Design 01 - series 03	Hole 01		Hole 02		Width		Depth		Length	
	Diam.	u	Diam.	u	Meas.	u	Meas.	u	Meas.	u
Channel 01	807,9	1,1	808,9	1,6	992,3	1,0	1 065,8	7,9	39 810,2	161,3
Channel 02	806,8	1,6	836,5	1,3	993,7	1,0	1 059,7	8,0	39 823,5	161,3
Channel 03	841,2	1,4	811,5	25,9	992,8	1,0	1 057,9	8,2	39 847,1	166,6
Leakage Channel					144,1	1,5	N/A	N/A	5 999,3	26,0

Measurement results obtained on the three series of the design 02:

Design 02 - series 01	Hole 01		Hole 02		Width		Depth		Length	
	Diam.	u	Diam.	u	Meas.	u	Meas.	u	Meas.	u
Channel 01	806,4	1,0	803,3	1,7	990,7	1,0	1 059,8	7,9	39 805,6	161,2
Channel 02	800,9	1,4	840,5	1,1	992,3	1,0	1 059,3	7,9	39 821,4	161,3
Channel 03	835,1	1,8	811,6	1,0	993,1	1,0	712,9	396,9	39 827,7	161,3
L Leakage Channel					142,1	1,0	N/A	N/A	5 998,7	26,0
R Leakage Channel					143,2	1,0	N/A	N/A	5 998,3	26,0

Design 02 - series 02	Hole 01		Hole 02		Width		Depth		Length	
	Diam.	u	Diam.	u	Meas.	u	Meas.	u	Meas.	u
Channel 01	808,0	1,0	811,0	1,0	992,4	1,0	1 066,6	8,0	40 835,6	165,3
Channel 02	807,6	1,0	840,1	1,1	990,6	1,0	1 062,4	7,9	39 827,7	161,3
Channel 03	839,2	2,1	810,9	1,1	988,7	1,0	362,6	395,7	39 827,8	161,3
L Leakage Channel					143,2	1,0	N/A	N/A	5 998,8	26,0
R Leakage Channel					143,1	1,0	N/A	N/A	5 998,2	26,0

Design 02 - series 03	Hole 01		Hole 02		Width		Depth		Length	
	Diam.	u	Diam.	u	Meas.	u	Meas.	u	Meas.	u
Channel 01	809,3	1,0	806,5	13,8	994,9	1,0	455,4	5,0	40 827,2	165,6
Channel 02	809,3	1,0	838,8	3,7	994,2	1,0	453,6	4,8	39 827,1	161,6
Channel 03	837,9	1,6	810,6	6,6	993,3	1,0	304,9	395,3	39 822,7	161,3
L Leakage Channel					143,1	1,0	N/A	N/A	5 999,3	26,0
R Leakage Channel					143,3	1,1	N/A	N/A	5 998,3	26,0

Measurement results obtained on the three series of the design 03:

Design 03 - series 01	Hole 01		Hole 02		Width		Depth		Length	
	Diam.	u	Diam.	u	Meas.	u	Meas.	u	Meas.	u
Channel 01	807,5	1,0	806,0	1,1	992,0	1,1	1 054,6	7,8	39 809,2	161,2
Channel 02			845,6	1,6	991,9	1,0	1 050,2	7,8	31 983,3	129,9
Channel 03			816,4	1,5	992,3	1,1	1 055,4	8,8	N/A	N/A
U Leakage Channel					145,0	1,0	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

Design 03 - series 02	Hole 01		Hole 02		Width		Depth		Length	
	Diam.	u	Diam.	u	Meas.	u	Meas.	u	Meas.	u
Channel 01	807,6	1,0	808,5	1,7	993,5	1,1	1 055,2	7,8	39 806,8	161,2
Channel 02			839,6	4,7	991,8	1,0	1 044,7	8,5	31 978,4	130,0
Channel 03			811,0	2,3	993,9	1,0	1 051,8	7,9	N/A	N/A
U Leakage Channel					145,1	1,0	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

Design 03 - series 03	Hole 01		Hole 02		Width		Depth		Length	
	Diam.	u	Diam.	u	Meas.	u	Meas.	u	Meas.	u
Channel 01	808,6	1,0	812,1	4,6	993,4	1,0	1 060,1	8,2	39 808,4	161,2
Channel 02			848,4	9,2	992,9	1,0	1 050,3	9,6	31 990,6	130,1
Channel 03			816,5	2,2	992,8	1,0	1 053,8	7,8	N/A	N/A
U Leakage Channel					145,0	1,0	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

Measurement results obtained on the three series of the design 04:

Design 04 - series 01	Hole 01		Hole 02		Width		Depth		Length	
	Diam.	u	Diam.	u	Meas.	u	Meas.	u	Meas.	u
Channel 01	807,7	1,0	836,7	1,4	992,9	1,0	1 064,2	8,4	39 822,0	161,3
Channel 02	806,6	1,0	838,9	2,1	993,6	1,1	1 059,6	8,1	39 822,4	161,3
Channel 03	835,4	4,7	806,4	4,0	993,0	1,1	1 061,4	8,0	39 822,5	161,3
Leakage Channel					144,3	1,0	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

Design 04 - series 02	Hole 01		Hole 02		Width		Depth		Length	
	Diam.	u	Diam.	u	Meas.	u	Meas.	u	Meas.	u
Channel 01	805,3	1,0	839,6	3,1	993,3	1,0	1 046,9	7,7	39 820,1	161,3
Channel 02	809,0	1,0	840,2	3,4	2 993,5	3 464,5	1 044,8	7,8	39 825,0	161,3
Channel 03	842,6	1,6	810,2	3,4	994,1	1,1	1 044,3	7,7	39 823,1	161,3
Leakage Channel					143,9	1,0	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

Design 04 - series 03	Hole 01		Hole 02		Width		Depth		Length	
	Diam.	u	Diam.	u	Meas.	u	Meas.	u	Meas.	u
Channel 01	807,8	1,0	836,6	1,1	992,7	1,0	1 052,0	8,3	39 821,8	161,3
Channel 02	805,5	1,0	837,4	1,8	992,7	1,0	1 048,1	8,0	39 822,4	161,3
Channel 03	836,4	1,1	812,2	5,0	993,4	1,0	1 050,1	8,3	39 822,8	161,3
Leakage Channel					144,1	1,0	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

Measurement results obtained on the three series of the design 05:

Design 05 - series 01	Hole 01		Hole 02		Width		Depth		Length	
	Diam.	u	Diam.	u	Meas.	u	Meas.	u	Meas.	u
Channel 01	809,3	1,0	808,2	5,9	990,3	1,0	1 061,3	8,6	39 814,8	161,3
L Channel 02	805,8	1,0			992,7	1,0	1 058,5	8,0	12 410,0	51,6
R Channel 02			842,0	1,1	987,6	1,0	1 051,2	7,9	12 411,3	51,7
L Channel 03	837,0	1,1			991,0	1,0	1 031,9	40,7	14 929,3	61,7
R Channel 03			808,1	3,3	988,1	1,0	1 072,0	11,1	14 894,8	61,6
L Channel 04	836,1	1,2			992,5	1,0	1 053,3	7,8	17 427,8	71,7
R Channel 04			835,7	1,3	988,0	1,0	1 053,8	8,0	17 409,5	71,6
Leakage Channel 02					144,2	1,0	N/A	N/A	15 993,7	66,2
Leakage Channel 03					144,1	1,0	N/A	N/A	10 998,9	46,0
Leakage Channel 04					144,1	1,0	N/A	N/A	5 999,4	26,0

Design 05 - series 02	Hole 01		Hole 02		Width		Depth		Length	
	Diam.	u	Diam.	u	Meas.	u	Meas.	u	Meas.	u
Channel 01	807,8	1,0	838,8	5,7	995,7	1,1	1 054,3	7,8	39 823,8	161,3
L Channel 02	808,7	1,0			992,4	1,0	1 049,3	7,9	12 410,7	51,6
R Channel 02			804,4	11,2	994,0	1,0	1 050,4	8,6	12 392,2	51,9
L Channel 03	836,0	1,0			993,6	1,0	1 063,1	8,2	14 924,9	61,7
R Channel 03			841,2	5,8	994,8	1,0	1 066,1	9,7	14 911,9	61,8
L Channel 04	836,8	1,1			992,6	1,0	1 047,0	8,1	17 426,1	71,7
R Channel 04			807,6	3,6	993,9	1,0	1 051,9	8,7	17 391,6	71,6
Leakage Channel 02					144,2	1,0	N/A	N/A	16 000,8	66,1
Leakage Channel 03					144,1	1,0	N/A	N/A	10 998,6	46,0
Leakage Channel 04					144,1	1,0	N/A	N/A	5 998,7	26,0

Design 05 - series 03	Hole 01		Hole 02		Width		Depth		Length	
	Diam.	u	Diam.	u	Meas.	u	Meas.	u	Meas.	u
Channel 01	806,7	1,0	840,5	2,8	988,2	1,0	1 062,9	8,2	39 825,8	161,3
L Channel 02	805,8	1,0			988,1	1,0	1 057,4	7,8	12 412,5	51,7
R Channel 02			812,6	2,7	991,7	1,1	1 059,5	7,9	12 393,9	51,6
L Channel 03	830,9	1,1			990,2	1,0	1 069,3	7,9	14 928,1	61,7
R Channel 03			841,8	1,7	990,7	1,0	1 069,1	8,5	14 909,7	61,7
L Channel 04	832,0	2,0			988,5	1,0	1 058,2	8,2	17 426,4	71,7
R Channel 04			807,0	1,5	991,6	1,0	1 053,6	8,0	17 391,0	71,6
Leakage Channel 02					144,2	1,0	N/A	N/A	15 999,0	66,0
Leakage Channel 03					144,2	1,0	N/A	N/A	10 999,9	46,0
Leakage Channel 04					144,2	1,0	N/A	N/A	6 000,5	26,0

Measurement results obtained on the two series of the design 06:

Design 06 - series 01	Hole 01		Hole 02		Width		Depth		Length	
	Diam.	u	Diam.	u	Meas.	u	Meas.	u	Meas.	u
Channel 01	793,3	1,0	822,9	15,6	988,4	1,1	1 092,9	8,0	39 808,2	161,4
Channel 02	794,0	1,0	837,6	8,7	988,1	1,0	1 095,7	8,0	39 820,6	161,5
Leakage Channel	803,9	1,4			144,6	1,0	N/A	N/A	6 429,0	27,8

Design 06 - series 02	Hole 01		Hole 02		Width		Depth		Length	
	Diam.	u	Diam.	u	Meas.	u	Meas.	u	Meas.	u
Channel 01	807,4	1,0	802,9	3,9	990,7	1,0	1 062,1	8,1	39 809,1	161,3
Channel 02	808,6	1,0	840,9	2,9	992,5	1,0	1 055,1	7,9	39 827,3	161,3
Leakage Channel	808,3	1,6			144,8	1,0	N/A	N/A	6 426,6	27,7

Measurement results obtained on the two series of the design 07:

Design 07 - series 01	Hole 01		Hole 02		Width		Depth		Length	
	Diam.	u	Diam.	u	Meas.	u	Meas.	u	Meas.	u
Channel 01	808,6	1,0	837,2	3,3	991,8	1,0	1 056,0	7,8	39 825,4	161,3
Channel 02	810,0	1,2	835,8	2,5	992,3	1,0	1 050,3	7,9	39 825,3	161,3
Leakage Channel	808,2	1,5			144,0	1,0	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

Design 07 - series 02	Hole 01		Hole 02		Width		Depth		Length	
	Diam.	u	Diam.	u	Meas.	u	Meas.	u	Meas.	u
Channel 01	805,4	1,0	842,4	1,3	989,8	1,1	1 062,9	7,9	39 827,0	161,3
Channel 02	806,8	1,0	841,5	3,4	987,8	1,0	1 059,6	7,9	39 831,7	161,4
Leakage Channel	808,1	1,1			144,5	1,0	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

Measurement results obtained on the design 08:

Design 08	Hole 01		Hole 02		Width		Depth		Length	
	Diam.	u	Diam.	u	Meas.	u	Meas.	u	Meas.	u
Channel 01	834,8	1,0	807,7	2,4	987,4	1,6	1 240,4	10,6	39 829,0	161,3
Bottom L Leakage Channel	835,7	1,0			143,8	1,0	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Bottom R Leakage Channel	837,6	1,5			143,5	1,0	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Top L Leakage Channel	804,3	1,1			144,6	1,0	N/A	N/A	8 888,4	37,6
Top R Leakage Channel	804,9	1,2			144,3	1,1	N/A	N/A	8 857,3	37,5

2.3.2. Volume

2.3.2.1. IPQ

2.3.2.1.1. Instrument

The measurement of the volume is done according to the protocol A2.4.3 with a weighing scale Mettler Toledo XP205 shown on Figure 10. The mass is then converted to volume based on the knowledge of the density of the water filling the channel.

Figure 10: Mettler Toledo XP205 used by IPQ.

2.3.2.1.2. Measurements

The volume was measured for one copy of each design of the glass chips. The channels are labelled as indicated in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Denomination of the channels for Table 4.

2.3.2.1.3. Data

The results are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Volume measurements obtained by IPQ.

Chip	Channel	Volume (mL)	Uncertainty (mL)
1-1	1	0.004266	0.000088
	1+2	0.00788	0.00018
	1+2+3	0.012255	0.000064
	Residual volume	0.000346	0.000076
1-2	1	0.004417	0.000037
	1+2	0.008630	0.000017
	1+2+3	0.01280	0.00014
	Residual volume	0.000361	0.000016
1-3	1	0.004359	0.000044
	1+2	0.00837	0.00016
	1+2+3	0.012401	0.000030
	Residual volume	0.000517	0.000017
2-1	1	0.004002	0.000077
	1+2	0.008254	0.000120
	1+2+3	0.012005	0.000041
	Residual volume	0.000430	0.000040
3-1	1	0.00444	0.00013
	Residual volume	0.000757	0.000032
3-2	1	0.00443	0.00012
	Residual volume	0.000752	0.000034
5-1	1	0.00442	0.00014
	Residual volume	0.000485	0.00012
6-2	1	0.004319	0.000082
	1+2	0.00806	0.00023
	Residual volume	0.000314	0.000056
7-1	1	0.00422	0.00014
	1+2	0.00824	0.00013
	Residual volume	0.000281	0.000040
8-1	1	0.00417	0.00015
	Residual volume	0.000205	0.000059

2.3.2.2. CETIAT

2.3.2.2.1. Instrument

A Sartorius weigh cell model WZ614-CW is used for this test, calibrated using Zwiebel standard weights of class E1, as seen on Figure 12.

Figure 12: Setup at CETIAT.

2.3.2.2.2. Measurements

CETIAT is not usually measuring the volume of microfluidic chips. However, as it is equipped with weighing scales appropriate for the measurement of microflows by gravimetric method, this weighing scale was used to get additional values to compare with IPQ. Because this weighing scale is designed to usually have a pre-load due to the weighing vessel for flow measurement, it requires a standard weight when measuring the mass of the glass transfer standards filled with water in order to reach the minimum weight of 400 g.

Figure 13: A standard weight is needed in addition to the chip to reach the minimum load of the scale.

The mass m_i of the liquid contained in channel i of the chip can be calculated as follows:

$$m_i = M_i - \frac{(M_{0,1} + M_{0,2})}{2}$$

With:

- M_i mass of the chip with water (reported in Table 5)
- $M_{0,1}$ mass of the empty chip at the start
- $M_{0,2}$ mass of the empty chip at the end

The average of $M_{0,1}$ and $M_{0,2}$ is used to account for the drift of the scale during the measurements.

The type uncertainty for one measurement of mass M is given by:

$$U^2(M) = u^2(\text{stability}) + u^2(\text{resolution}) + u^2(\text{drift}) + u^2(\text{calibration})$$

In the present case, the evaluation of this formula yields:

$$U^2(M) = \left(\frac{\sigma_M}{\sqrt{6}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{0,0001}{2\sqrt{3}}\right)^2 + |M_{0,1} - M_{0,2}|^2 + u^2(\text{standard weight})$$

Given the formula of mass m_i , its associated type uncertainty is thus:

$$U^2(m_i) = U^2(M_i) + \left(\frac{1}{2}U(M_{0,1})\right)^2 + \left(\frac{1}{2}U(M_{0,2})\right)^2$$

To compute the volume V , the mass m of water contained in the chip (reported in Table 6) is divided by the density ρ of the liquid:

$$V = \frac{m}{\rho}$$

Hence the type uncertainty for volume according to the rule of uncertainty propagation:

$$U^2(V) = \left(\left|\frac{\partial V}{\partial m}\right| u(m)\right)^2 + \left(\left|\frac{\partial V}{\partial \rho}\right| u(\rho)\right)^2$$

For these measurements, ultra-pure degassed water was used with a density of 998.2 kg/m³ and a type uncertainty ($k=1$) of 0.1 kg/m³.

The values of the calculated volumes are presented in Table 7.

2.3.2.2.1. Data

Table 5: Indications of mass read on the weighing scale for chips 1-1 and 1-3 with the pre-load mass, with the average mass and the corrected mass to account for drift.

Setup	Channel	Iteration 1 (g)	Iteration 2 (g)	Iteration 3 (g)	Iteration 4 (g)	Iteration 5 (g)	Iteration 6 (g)	Average (g)	σ (g)	Corrected (g)
Standard weight alone	-	499.9990	499.9991	499.9991	499.9991	499.9991	499.9990	499.9991	0.00005	499.99989
1-1	0	503.3263	503.3264	503.3263	503.3264	503.3264	503.3264	503.3264	0.00005	503.3274
1-1	1	503.3308	503.3308	503.3308	503.3308	503.3307	503.3307	503.3308	0.00005	503.3318
1-1	2	503.3311	503.3312	503.3311	503.3310	503.3310	503.3310	503.3311	0.00008	503.3321
1-1	1+2	503.3353	503.3353	503.3353	503.3353	503.3352	503.3352	503.3353	0.00005	503.3363
1-1	3	503.3308	503.3307	503.3307	503.3307	503.3307	503.3306	503.3307	0.00006	503.3317
1-1	0	503.3260	503.3260	503.3260	503.3260	503.3260	503.3260	503.3260	0.00000	503.3270
Standard weight alone	-	499.9987	499.9987	499.9987	499.9987	499.9987	499.9987	499.9987	0.00000	499.99989
1-3	0	503.3336	503.3336	503.3336	503.3336	503.3336	503.3336	503.3336	0.00000	503.3348
1-3	1	503.3383	503.3384	503.3384	503.3383	503.3384	503.3383	503.3384	0.00005	503.3396
1-3	1+2	503.3429	503.3429	503.3429	503.3430	503.3429	503.3428	503.3429	0.00006	503.3441
1-3	1+2+3	503.3482	503.3482	503.3481	503.3481	503.3481	503.3479	503.3481	0.00011	503.3493
1-3	2	503.3387	503.3387	503.3387	503.3387	503.3386	503.3387	503.3387	0.00004	503.3399
1-3	2+3	503.3428	503.3428	503.3428	503.3429	503.3428	503.3428	503.3428	0.00004	503.3440
1-3	3	503.3384	503.3383	503.3383	503.3383	503.3383	503.3383	503.3383	0.00004	503.3395
1-3	0	503.3337	503.3337	503.3338	503.3338	503.3337	503.3337	503.3337	0.00005	503.3349
Standard weight alone	-	499.9986	499.9986	499.9987	499.9987	499.9987	499.9987	499.9987	0.00005	499.99989

Table 6: Mass of water contained by each channel of chips 1-1 and 1-3, after subtraction of the pre-load mass, and the associated uncertainty components.

Chip	Channel	m (mg)	U _{k=2} (mg)	Uncertainty components (k=1) (mg)									
				Chip with water				Empty chip 1			Empty chip 2		
				stability	resolution	drift	calibration	stability	resolution	calibration	stability	resolution	calibration
1-1	1	4.58	0.74	0.021	0.029	0.367	0.040	0.021	0.029	0.040	0.000	0.029	0.040
	2	4.88	0.75	0.033	0.029	0.367	0.040	0.021	0.029	0.040	0.000	0.029	0.040
	1+2	9.08	0.74	0.021	0.029	0.367	0.040	0.021	0.029	0.040	0.000	0.029	0.040
	3	4.52	0.75	0.026	0.029	0.367	0.040	0.021	0.029	0.040	0.000	0.029	0.040
1-3	1	4.68	0.30	0.022	0.029	0.133	0.040	0.000	0.029	0.040	0.021	0.029	0.040
	1+2	9.23	0.30	0.026	0.029	0.133	0.040	0.000	0.029	0.040	0.021	0.029	0.040
	1+2+3	14.43	0.31	0.045	0.029	0.133	0.040	0.000	0.029	0.040	0.021	0.029	0.040
	2	5.02	0.30	0.017	0.029	0.133	0.040	0.000	0.029	0.040	0.021	0.029	0.040
	2+3	9.15	0.30	0.017	0.029	0.133	0.040	0.000	0.029	0.040	0.021	0.029	0.040
	3	4.65	0.30	0.017	0.029	0.133	0.040	0.000	0.029	0.040	0.021	0.029	0.040

Table 7: Volumes calculated for chips 1-1 and 1-3, with the associated expanded uncertainty (k=2).

Chip	Channel	V (μL)	U _{k=2} (μL)
1-1	1	4.59	1.49
	2	4.89	1.50
	1+2	9.10	1.49
	3	4.52	1.49
1-3	1	4.69	0.59
	1+2	9.25	0.60
	1+2+3	14.46	0.61
	2	5.03	0.59
	2+3	9.17	0.59
	3	4.66	0.59

2.3.3. Hydrodynamic resistance

Although the proper term of the quantity is “hydrodynamic resistance”, it is also commonly referred to as “flow resistivity”, “hydraulic resistance”, or “hydraulic resistivity”. These terms are sometimes used in the following sections, but they always refer to the same quantity.

2.3.3.1. DTI

Preliminary report compiling results from work aiming to determine the hydraulic resistance of microchannels in microfluidic chips. The measurements were made with persistent work during 11/12/2024 - 21/12/2023, using the nanoflow setup in the microflow laboratory at the Danish Technological Institute (DTI), and using the glass transfer standards created by the MFMET project.

2.3.3.1.1. Materials and methods

The chips worked with were chip 1-1, chip 2-1, chip 3-1, and chip 4-1. See Table 10 for further details. The setup for measuring hydraulic resistivity at the nanoflow system in the microflow laboratory at DTI is like the setup for testing flow resistivity (i.e., hydraulic resistivity) displayed in the MFMET protocol A2.4.3

2.3.3.1.2. Evaluation of uncertainty

The below paragraphs describe how the uncertainties were calculated for the measurements of flow and pressure. Each measurement simultaneously measured flow and pressure, and it was repeated three times.

The uncertainties of the flow measurements determined with the gravimetric reference is evaluated with the following contributions. First, the CMC value of the gravimetric reference. This describes uncertainty from the gravimetric reference. Second, the repeated flow measurements’ experimental standard deviation of the mean, as defined under type A uncertainty in the Guide to the expression of Uncertainty in Measurement (GUM) [4]. This describes uncertainty from the ability to repeat measurements.

The uncertainty of the flow measurements determined with the Sensirion SLI-1000 flowmeter was evaluated with the following contributions. First, the stated accuracy of the flowmeter. This describes uncertainty from the flowmeter. Second, each repeated flow measurement produced a time series of flow values. For these time series the data analysis calculated means and experimental standard deviations, as defined by type A uncertainty in the GUM. The experimental standard deviations were propagated to the uncertainty of the mean of these means of time series, see the GUM. This described uncertainty from scattering of time series signals. Third, the mean of the time series means had an experimental standard deviation of the mean calculated, as defined under type A uncertainty in the GUM. This described uncertainty from the ability to repeat measurements.

The uncertainty of the pressure measurements determined with the Fluigent pressure unit S and Fluigent pressure unit S was evaluated with the following contributions. First, the stated accuracy of

the pressure sensor. This described uncertainty from the pressure sensor. Second, each repeated pressure measurement produced a time series of pressure values. For the time series the data analysis calculated means and experimental standard deviations, as defined by type A uncertainty in the GUM. The experimental standard deviations were propagated to the uncertainty of the mean of these means of time series, see the GUM. This describes uncertainty from scattering of time series signals. Third, the mean of these time series means had an experimental standard deviation of the mean calculated, as defined under type A uncertainty in the GUM. This described uncertainty from the ability to repeat measurements.

2.3.3.1.3. Fitting of polynomials

The fitting of polynomials was made with the python module `scipy.odr` [6]. This module performs fitting with orthogonal distance regression, which considers errors on the dependent variable and errors on the independent variable. E.g., errors on both flow and pressure.

2.3.3.1.4. Results

Table 10 lists the measurements made on the glass transfer chips, while at the microflow laboratory at DTI.

Table 8: Results from measurements of paired values of flow and pressure. In the setup column: system refers to measurements of the nanoflow system without the chip, main refers the nanoflow system and a chip with flow through a main channel, leakage refers the nanoflow system and a chip with flow through a leakage channel.

Data ID	Chip	Setup	Flowmeter	Pressure sensor	Flow ($\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$)	Flow unc. (k=1) ($\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$)	Pressure (mbar)	Pressure unc. (k=1) (mbar)
3011	1-1	System	Sensirion SLI-1000	Fluigent pressure unit S	1018.	26.	62.8	1.5
					820.	21.	51.9	1.6
					620.	16.	40.8	1.5
					418.	11.	29.9	1.8
					209.	5.4	18.1	1.5
3012	1-1	Main	Sensirion SLI-1000	Fluigent pressure unit S	1034.	27.	170.1	2.4
					833.	21.	144.4	2.4
					629.	16.	111.5	5.4
					424.	11.	83.5	3.8
					208.3	6.6	47.8	4.4
3014, 3015	1-1	Leakage	Gravimetric reference	Fluigent pressure unit XL	0.2867	0.0016	4044.	148.
					0.1941	0.0014	4564.	209.
					0.09416	0.0005	3178.	159.
					0.00062	0.00031	232.	33.
3018	2-1	System	Sensirion SLI-1000	Fluigent pressure unit S	1022.	26.	62.2	1.5
					824.	21.	51.3	1.6
					622.	16.	40.5	1.5
					419.	11.	30.1	1.6
					209.2	5.4	19.6	1.5
3017	2-1	Main	Sensirion SLI-1000	Fluigent pressure unit S	1026.	26.	161.	1.6
					826.	21.	128.7	1.6
					624.	16.	99.4	1.6
					419.	11.	70.1	1.5
					209.3	5.5	39.8	1.6
3020, 3021	2-1	Leakage	Gravimetric reference	Fluigent pressure unit XL	0.2683	0.0053	2578.	446.
					0.2527	0.0017	4720.	112.
					0.15877	0.00087	3891.	133.
					0.09272	0.00053	5325.	244.

					0.000007	0.000051	192.	28.
3023	3-1	System	Sensirion SLI-1000	Fluigent pressure unit S	1027. 827. 625. 421. 208.8	26. 21. 16. 11. 5.6	72.4 57.3 46.6 35.6 23.2	2.6 2. 1.9 2. 3.2
3022	3-1	Main	Sensirion SLI-1000	Fluigent pressure unit S	1031. 831. 626. 422. 210.3	30. 24. 18. 13. 6.	182.8 148.5 124. 101. 54.4	1.7 1.7 4.2 4.3 4.6
3024	3-1	Leakage	Gravimetri c reference	Fluigent pressure unit XL	0.2738 0.25 0.1911 0.16224 0.10663 0.00587	0.0032 0.0028 0.0011 0.00097 0.00078 0.0003	4605. 4256. 3339. 2911. 1968. 124.	54. 40. 21. 22. 28. 20.
3028	4-1	System	Sensirion SLI-1000	Fluigent pressure unit S	50.7 209.7 420. 625. 828. 1027.	1.5 5.5 11. 16. 21. 26.	12.1 21.4 32.3 42.4 54.6 68.2	1.7 1.6 1.6 1.8 2.4 2.
3029	4-1	System	Sensirion SLI-1000	Fluigent pressure unit S	1028. 828. 628. 417. 210.2 51.5	27. 21. 17. 11. 5.9 1.5	70.5 56.8 41.3 31.4 20.7 12.6	2.8 2.1 2.5 2.2 1.8 1.8
3025	4-1	Main	Sensirion SLI-1000	Fluigent pressure unit S	50.7 209.8 421. 624. 827. 1026.	1.5 5.5 11. 16. 21. 26.	15.5 44.8 72.7 103.2 128.7 157.2	1.8 1.5 1.5 1.6 1.6 1.6
3026	4-1	Main	Sensirion SLI-1000	Fluigent pressure unit S	1029. 827. 624. 420. 209.7 50.7	26. 22. 16. 11. 5.6 1.4	155.8 128.9 100.3 69. 45.2 13.3	1.7 1.8 1.7 1.9 2.8 1.5
4030	4-1	Leakage	Gravimetri c reference	Fluigent pressure unit XL	0.04711 0.0856 0.1181 0.1457	0.00034 0.00057 0.0014 0.0021	1989. 3900. 4128. 4173.	21. 38. 72. 68.
4031	4-1	Leakage	Gravimetri c reference	Fluigent pressure unit XL	0.12927 0.0985 0.07 0.04256 0.0248	0.00089 0.0017 0.0011 0.00031 0.00041	3750. 2937. 2275. 1632. 1118.	20. 22. 20. 32. 22.

Figure 14 shows data from two selected pairs of chip and setup in Table 10. Mostly, the setups with flow through the system only (no chip) or setups with flow through a main channel of a chip yielded results with fair resemblance of a linear relationship between flow and pressure.

Figure 14: Measured values and fits for flow and pressure for chip 1-1 with setups system (Data ID 3011) and main (Data ID 3012). Error bars are shown with $k=1$.

Figure 15 shows data from two selected pairs of chip and setup in Table 10. Mostly, the setups with flow through a leakage channel of a chip yielded results with great scatter, and no clear relationship between flow and pressure. However, the data with data ID 4031, is an exception to this tendency, see Figure 15.

Figure 15: Measured values of flow and pressure and fits for chip 2-1 with setup leakage (Data ID 3020, 3021) and chip 4-1 with setup leakage (Data ID 4031). Error bars are shown with $k=1$.

Figure 16 and Figure 17 shows time series recorded from the balance of the gravimetric reference and the pressure sensor. Figure 16 corresponds to the data with great scattering in Figure 15, and in Figure 16 there are obvious changes in the pressure during periods of constant flow. Figure 17 corresponds to the data with less scatter in Figure 15, and in Figure 17 the pressure is more stable than in Figure 16. Notice that the different durations of measurement time make this comparison more difficult.

Figure 16: Signals from selected instruments of the nanoflow system: the balance, a Sensirion SLI-430 flow meter (not used), and a Fluigent pressure unit XL. The signals are from data ID 3020, 3021, chip 2-1. The duration of each measurement is 6000 seconds.

Figure 17: Signals from selected instruments of the nanoflow system: the balance, a Sensirion SLI-430 flow meter (not used), and a Fluigent pressure unit XL. The signals are from data ID 4031, chip 4-1. The duration of each measurement is 300 seconds.

Table 9 shows the results of fitting 1st order polynomials to the data in Table 10. A few of these 1st order polynomials can be seen in Figure 14 and Figure 15. The fit was considered statistically significant if it can pass a chi-square test for goodness of fit [3]. In the case of a significant fit, the parameter m_1 (the linear slope) is interpreted as the hydraulic resistivity. The hydraulic resistivity of a main channel or leakage channel, without the system, can be determined by subtracting the associated hydraulic resistivity of the system.

Table 9: Results from fits to the measured paired values of flow and pressure in Table 10. The fit is a 1st order polynomial where m_0 is a parameter for a constant term, and m_1 is a parameter for a linear slope term. From the fits that can pass a chi-square test for goodness of fit (Gof-test), a hydraulic resistance was inferred from the fit parameter m_1 (the slope of the 1st order polynomial).

Data ID	Chip	Setup	m_0 (mbar)	m_0 unc. ($k=1$) (mbar)	m_1 (mbar/ μ L/min)	m_1 unc. ($k=1$) (mbar/ μ L/min)	Statistics (χ^2 , dof, p-value)	Gof-test (p-value>0.05)	RH (mbar/ μ L/min)	RH unc. ($k=1$) (mbar/ μ L/min)
3011	1-1	System	6.6	1.8	0.0552	0.0029	0.018, 3, 1.0	Pass	0.0552	0.0029
3012	1-1	Main	18.8	4.8	0.1486	0.0067	0.80, 3, 0.85	Pass	0.1486	0.0067
3014, 3015	1-1	Leakage	271.	33.	16019.	477.	141, 2, 0.0	Fail	N/A	N/A
3018	2-1	System	8.4	1.8	0.0523	0.0028	0.15, 3, 0.99	Pass	0.0523	0.0028
3017	2-1	Main	8.9	2.3	0.1462	0.0043	0.41, 3, 0.94	Pass	0.1462	0.0043
3020, 3021	2-1	Leakage	229.	28.	19277.	414.	254, 3, 0.0	Fail	N/A	N/A
3023	3-1	System	10.6	2.9	0.0583	0.0044	0.90, 3, 0.83	Pass	0.0583	0.0044
3022	3-1	Main	29.1	5.	0.1485	0.0073	6.6, 3, 0.086	Pass	0.1487	0.0072
3024	3-1	Leakage	9.	21.	17524.	152.	28, 4, 0.0	Fail	N/A	N/A
3028	4-1	System	9.1	1.3	0.0557	0.0025	1.3, 4, 0.86	Pass	0.0556	0.0025
3029	4-1	System	8.6	1.5	0.0574	0.0028	3.0, 4, 0.55	Pass	0.0574	0.0028
3025	4-1	Main	11.3	1.5	0.1449	0.0034	7.4, 4, 0.12	Pass	0.1449	0.0034
3026	4-1	Main	7.5	1.5	0.1471	0.0033	7.4, 4, 0.12	Pass	0.1471	0.0033
4030	4-1	Leakage	487.	53.	33517.	778.	335, 2, 0.0	Fail	N/A	N/A
4031	4-1	Leakage	519.	26.	24972.	345.	3.8, 3, 0.29	Pass	24972.	345.

As seen in Table 10, Table 9, Figure 15, and Figure 16, these experiments experienced obvious variations of pressure during measurements of flow through leakage channels. To investigate this further, time series from the balance and pressure sensor was recorded over approximately 10½ hours, see Figure 18. Initially, the syringe pump was set to 0.033 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$, and at 22:15 the 21st of December 2023 the syringe pump was stopped. Slow decays of mass flow and pressure followed, and it looks as though the decays have not stopped after 10 hours, when the recording stops. It could be that with a syringe pump and leakage channels of size 150 μm x 2 μm , a very long time is required for the system to reach equilibrium.

Figure 18: Signals from selected instruments of the nanoflow system: the balance, a Sensirion SLI-430 flow meter (not used), and a Fluigent pressure unit XL. The signals are from data ID 4032, chip 4-1. The duration of the time series is about 10½ hours. This measurement was different from the other measurements series, and thus data ID 4032 is not listed in Table 10 and Table 9. The syringe pump was initially set to 0.033 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$, and at 22:15 the 21st of December 2023 the syringe pump was stopped.

2.3.3.1.5. Discussion

One can argue for some confidence in the results regarding flow through the nanoflow system only, or flow through the nanoflow system and a main channel of a microfluidic chip.

There is less confidence in the results regarding flow through a leakage channel. Even for data ID 4031 chip 4-1, which did pass the chi-square test for goodness of fit, it is concerning that the equivalent test with data ID 4030 chip 4-1 yielded very different results. One reason could be that when adjusting the flow with the syringe pump it takes a long time, compared to the waiting time and measurement time in the experiment, for flow and pressure to equilibrate. Furthermore, Figure 18 suggests the time to

equilibrate to be longer than 10 hours. This relatively long time could have something to do with the system only being able to communicate with the surroundings through a channel of size $150\ \mu\text{m} \times 2\ \mu\text{m}$. Considering that the time to equilibrate may be longer than the duration of measurements of data ID for 4031 chip 4-1, it is not guaranteed that these measurements represent flow in equilibrium, they could also represent the adjustments and decisions of the experimentalist.

It is speculated that perhaps some data analysis can be devised for the decays of mass flow and pressure in Figure 18, which can derive the hydraulic resistance or some other use parameter.

2.3.3.2. University of Glasgow

2.3.3.2.1. Materials and methods

The chips worked with were chip 1-1, chip 2-1, chip 3-1, chip 4-2, chip 5-1, chip 6-2, chip 7-1 and chip 8-1 for the main channels and chip 4-2 and chip 6-2 for leakage channels. See Table 10 for further details.

The setup for measuring hydraulic resistivity ARC was similar to the setup for testing flow resistivity (i.e., hydraulic resistivity) displayed in the MFMET protocol A2.4.3. However, some changes have been made for specific measurements.

2.3.3.2.1.1. Experimental setup for main channels

For the main channel, syringe pump (PHD ultra, Harvard apparatus) was used to drive the flow at a fixed flow rate. 2.5 ml syringe (SGE syringe) was used. One of the pressure sensor from Fluigent system (Fluigent MFCS-EZ) was connected at a T-junction just before the chip to measure the pressure. At the outlet, flow meter (Sensirion SLF-3S-0600F) was connected to measure the flow rate. Figure 19 shows schematic of the system used to characterise the main channel of glass chips. Fluigent software (OxyGEN 2.3) was used to record pressure readings and USB/RS485 sensor viewer 2.91 was used to measure flow rates.

Figure 19: Schematic of flow measurement system for main channel

2.3.3.2.1.2. Experimental setup for leakage channels

For the leak channel, different configuration was established as shown in Figure 20. Syringe pump (PHD ultra, Harvard apparatus) was used to drive the flow at a fixed flow rate. 100 μL syringe (ILS Germany) was used. Because of high fluidic resistance in leak channel and limit of pressure sensor available in the laboratory, a different approach was used to measure pressure. A 250 μL syringe (Hamilton gastight 1725) was fixed on the top of weighing balance (Sartorius practum) using a retort stand. Once the pressure is established in the system, it exerts pressure inside the syringe and equivalent weight is measured. Using the barrel area of the syringe and weight, one can calculate the pressure. It is to note that there is some stiction force acting in opposite direction. Therefore, a simple experiment was conducted first to measure stiction force. Weighing balance starts to display weight once the stiction force of the syringe is overcome. A flowmeter (Sensirion SLI-0430) was connected in front of syringe that measures pressure to confirm if there is any flow towards pressure measuring syringe. For the flow rate, a low flowrate measuring flowmeter (Sensirion LG16-0150D) was connected at the outlet of the chip. Fluident software (OxyGEN 2.3) was used to record pressure readings and USB/RS485 sensor viewer 2.91 was used to measure flow rates. A LabVIEW program was developed to record weights.

Figure 20: Schematic of flow measurement system for leakage channel

Figure 21: Photograph of the set up

2.3.3.2.1.3. Experimental setup for measuring stiction

A 250 μL syringe (Hamilton gastight 1725) was used for stiction measurement experiment. Syringe was half-filled using DI water and was fixed vertically downwards using a retort stand. After fixing, a beaker was placed on the top end of syringe. Water was slowly placed in the beaker, while observing both motion of the plunger and water at the outlet of the tip. Water was added until plunger started to move, and water was visible at the outlet. At this point, the total weight of beaker along with water was weighed. Measurements were done three times, and the results were averaged. For the syringe used in the experiment, stiction force was measured to be approximately 24.59 g.

Figure 22: Measurement of stiction force A. schematics B. Actual image of the set up

2.3.3.2.2. Evaluation of uncertainty

The uncertainty of the flow measurements from Sensirion SLI-1000 flowmeter is evaluated with the following contributions. First, the stated accuracy of the flowmeter. This describes uncertainty from the flowmeter. Second, each repeated flow measurement produces a time series of flow values. For these time series, the data analysis calculates means and experimental standard deviations, as defined by type A uncertainty in the GUM (JCGM, 2008). The experimental standard deviations are propagated to the uncertainty of the mean of these means of time series. This describes uncertainty from scattering of time series signals. Third, the mean of the time series means has an experimental standard deviation of the mean calculated, as defined under type A uncertainty in the GUM (JCGM, 2008). This describes uncertainty from the ability to repeat measurements.

The uncertainty of the pressure measurements determined with the Fluigent pressure unit MFCS-EZ is evaluated with the following contributions. First, the stated accuracy of the pressure sensor. This describes uncertainty from the pressure sensor from the Fluigent unit. Second, each repeated pressure measurement produces a time series of pressure values. For the time series the data analysis calculates means and experimental standard deviations, as defined by type A uncertainty in the GUM (JCGM, 2008). The experimental standard deviations are propagated to the uncertainty of the mean of these means of time series. This describes uncertainty from scattering of time series signals. Third, the mean of these time series means has an experimental standard deviation of the mean calculated, as defined under type A uncertainty in the GUM (JCGM, 2008). This describes uncertainty from the ability to repeat measurements.

The uncertainties of the pressure measurement using weighing method (Sartorius Praxium) is evaluated with the following contributions. First, the stated accuracy of the weighing balance. This describes uncertainty from the balance. Second, the repeated weight measurements' experimental standard deviation of the mean, as defined under type A uncertainty in the Guide to the expression of Uncertainty in Measurement in the GUM (JCGM, 2008). This describes uncertainty from the ability to repeat measurements.

2.3.3.2.3. Fitting of polynomials

The fitting of polynomials is made with the python module `scipy.odr` (The SciPy community, 2024). This module performs fitting with orthogonal distance regression, which considers errors on the dependent variable and errors on the independent variable. E.g., errors on both flow and pressure.

2.3.3.2.4. Results

2.3.3.2.4.1. Hydraulic resistivity for main channels

Experiments were carried out with various flow rates ranging from 200 $\mu\text{l}/\text{min}$ to 1000 $\mu\text{l}/\text{min}$. A fixed flow was provided using the syringe pump and the data were recorded from the beginning. Initially, the flow and pressure rise with time and become stable after certain time interval. It was seen that

for higher flow rate, flow and pressure values were stable in a very short amount of time compared to the experiments with lower flow rate. For the analysis, data were used only after pressure and flow values were observed to be stable.

Figure 23 shows time series recorded from the pressure sensor and flow sensor. The plot shown in the figure corresponds to one of the experiments for chip 2-1 (main) at flow rate of 619.78 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$. The flow and pressure become stable after certain time depending on the flowrate. Initially, all the air present inside the channel gets compressed and the pressure rises until it becomes stable. Data in Table 1 were obtained after the pressure and flow becomes stable.

Figure 23: Signals from two selected instruments: Flow sensor, a Sensirion SLF-3S-0600F and Fluigent pressure unit MFCS-EZ. The signals are from Chip 2-1 (main) at a flow rate of 619.78 (experiment 1).

Table 10 lists the measurements made on the glass transfer chips, while at the university of Glasgow. Experimental set up was used as explained in Section 2.3.3.2.1.1. During the experiments, flow was provided using the syringe pump and the corresponding pressure was measured. A flow meter was used to measure flow through the channels. After the measurements, data was plotted using python using orthogonal regression and the slope was calculated which provides the resistivity of the channel (or system).

Table 10: Results from measurements of paired values of flow and pressure. In the setup column: system refers to measurements of the system without the chip, main refers the system and a chip with flow through a main channel, leakage refers the system and a chip with flow through a leakage channel.

Chip	Setup	Flowmeter	Pressure sensor	Flow (ul/min)	Flow unc (ul/min)	Pressure (mbar)	Pressure unc (mbar)
1-1	system	Sensirion SLF-3S-0600F	Fluigent (MFCS-EZ)	207.70	2.89	30.08	0.15
				413.90	4.41	36.13	0.11
				616.17	6.00	50.39	0.20
				808.22	6.35	63.83	0.49
				1001.06	9.04	78.57	0.24
1-1	main	Sensirion SLF-3S-0600F	Fluigent (MFCS-EZ)	206.26	2.43	47.82	0.21
				418.21	3.14	83.78	0.21
				619.18	4.50	107.37	0.15
				818.52	5.12	140.04	0.20
				1009.07	6.49	171.48	0.17
2-1	system	Sensirion SLF-3S-0600F	Fluigent (MFCS-EZ)	209.46	2.35	22.79	0.33
				416.59	3.26	36.07	0.12
				619.79	3.71	49.88	0.14
				815.58	4.75	65.94	0.27
				1000.48	5.70	77.60	0.15
2-1	main	Sensirion SLF-3S-0600F	Fluigent (MFCS-EZ)	209.46	2.35	45.60	0.28
				416.59	3.26	82.21	0.23
				619.79	3.71	117.63	0.20
				815.58	4.75	152.12	0.27
				1000.48	5.70	185.08	0.18
3-1	main	Sensirion SLF-3S-0600F	Fluigent (MFCS-EZ)	208.36	2.16	44.45	0.27
				412.64	3.01	79.86	0.19
				617.71	3.88	115.40	0.22
				816.98	4.62	156.88	0.26
				999.87	5.89	185.14	0.26
4-1	main	Sensirion SLF-3S-0600F	Fluigent (MFCS-EZ)	217.49	2.33	44.25	0.25
				410.65	3.32	81.62	0.25
				606.51	4.39	117.22	0.26
				801.84	4.68	147.48	0.35
				983.15	5.97	179.54	0.26
5-1	main	Sensirion SLF-3S-0600F	Fluigent (MFCS-EZ)	207.18	2.07	44.25	0.25
				413.22	3.47	81.62	0.25
				611.54	4.15	117.22	0.26
				802.34	4.93	147.48	0.35
				990.29	5.97	179.54	0.26
6-2	main	Sensirion SLF-3S-0600F	Fluigent (MFCS-EZ)	199.42	2.59	44.11	0.31
				394.58	3.11	79.57	0.24
				587.62	4.17	115.90	0.19
				778.64	5.29	148.14	0.17
				961.99	6.36	179.73	0.23
7-1	main	Sensirion SLF-3S-0600F	Fluigent (MFCS-EZ)	208.52	2.25	38.82	0.16
				412.36	3.37	72.94	0.19
				609.43	5.06	107.74	0.21
				806.38	5.63	153.39	0.24
				991.92	6.33	181.45	0.34
8-1	main	Sensirion SLF-3S-0600F	Fluigent (MFCS-EZ)	196.75	2.52	15.48	0.15
				376.95	2.74	27.15	0.19
				543.63	4.22	53.85	0.28
				692.90	16.04	84.56	0.42
				837.10	3.91	105.31	0.20

Figure 24 shows data from chip 2-1 and setup. Mostly, the setups with flow through the system only (no chip) or setups with flow through a main channel of a chip yielded results with fair resemblance of a linear relationship between flow and pressure. Slope of the fitted curve provides hydraulic resistance of the system including chip. The resistivity was measured to be 0.1760 mbar/ μ L/min for chip 2-1. Summarized results for hydraulic resistivity for all chips used during the experiments are shown in Table 11.

Figure 24: Measured values and fits for flow and pressure for chip 2-1 with setups system and main.

Table 11: Hydraulic resistivity for different main channels and system

Chip	Setup	Resistivity (mbar/ μ L/min)	Resistivity Unc (mbar/ μ L/min)	Intercept (mbar)	Intercept Unc (mbar)
1-1	system	0.0620	0.0052	13.5188	3.5039
1-1	main	0.1513	0.0047	17.1500	3.2093
2-1	system	0.0704	0.0017	7.3426	1.1589
2-1	main	0.1760	0.0003	8.6931	0.2388
3-1	main	0.1803	0.0039	6.1080	2.6879
4-1	main	0.1750	0.0038	8.3180	2.5325
5-1	main	0.1721	0.0025	9.8927	1.6673
6-2	main	0.1780	0.0021	9.4403	1.3862
7-1	main	0.1865	0.0066	-2.1220	4.3975
8-1	main	0.1475	0.0143	-20.8700	8.2837

2.3.3.2.4.2. Hydraulic resistivity for leakage channels

A separate approach was used while performing experiments with leakage channels. Because of limit of pressure sensor that was available in our lab, we used balance to measure the weight which occurs

due to the pressure in the system. The set up is described in Section 2.3.3.2.1.2. Before doing the experiments, a calibration was performed between weight and pressure. Figure 27 represents calibration of syringe for different applied pressure values. Briefly, a fixed pressure was applied through the Fluigent pressure pump and corresponding changes in weight in balance was recorded. The syringe started to move only after stiction coefficient was overcome. Section 2.3 presents the experimental process for measuring the stiction value. For these sets of experiments, movement of syringe plunger was observed after the pressure was higher than 650 mbar. From the analysis, it was observed that for every 22.73 mbar pressure, there was change of 1 g in the balance. However, theoretical calculations show 24 mbar of pressure is needed to change a weight in balance by 1 g. This also adds some level of uncertainty during resistivity measurement of leakage channel using our approach. Figure 25 represents calibration of syringe for different applied pressure. Pressure was applied through the Fluigent pressure pump and corresponding changes in weight in balance was recorded. The syringe started to move only after stiction coefficient was overcome. For these sets of experiments, movement of syringe plunger was observed after the pressure was higher than 650 mbar. From the analysis, it was observed that for every 22.73 mbar pressure, there was change of 1 g in the balance. However, theoretical calculations show 24 mbar of pressure is needed to change a weight in balance by 1 g. This also adds some level of uncertainty during resistivity measurement of leakage channel using our approach.

Figure 25: Measured weight for applied pressure for syringe used during experiments with leakage channels.

After performing the stiction test and calibration, experiments were performed for leakage channels. Unlike experiment with main channels where discrete value of flow was provided and corresponding pressure was measured, we performed pressure decay experiments for leakage channels. We used a syringe pump to deliver the flow while measuring the flow rate and weights in the balance. The flow was provided until a stable value of weight was obtained. At this condition, the flow value at the outlet

of leakage channel was nearly the flow provided by the pump. After obtaining a stable value, we stopped the pump and pressure decay was recorded continuously. We also performed experiments with much lower flow rate such as $0.05 \mu\text{l}/\text{min}$ which took a very long time to become stable. One could try these experiments under the condition that there is absolutely no leakage in the system. Additionally, to avoid leakage in the system due to much higher pressure built up, we have limited the flow values to less than $0.4 \mu\text{l}/\text{min}$ depending on the chip used. Figure 26 represents (A) pressure and (B) average flow plots for every 10 s for the experiments performed with Chip 6-2 (experiment 3). These plots are the results of pressure decay experiments which resulted in stable results. Small break in the flow curve is due to the passage of air bubble through the flow rate.

Figure 26: A and B represents pressure and average flow measurement for every 10 seconds from the pressure decay experiments for chip 6-2 (experiment 3).

Figure 27 shows the pressure-flow plot for leakage channel of chip 6-2. Pressure recordings were done in terms of weight in grams. Weight readings were converted to equivalent pressure using calibration curve as discussed above in this section and were plotted against corresponding flow rates. The slope of the curves gives inverse hydraulic resistance. Intercept for different experiments were different because of presence of air bubbles trapped inside the channel and the system. Once all the air got compressed, pressure rises significantly reaching some stable value. The sudden interrupt in curve is due to tiny bubble flowing through the flow meter.

Figure 27: Measured values of flow rate at various pressure for leakage channel, and fits for chip 6-2 for 3 repeated experiments; (A) experiment 1 (B) experiment 2 and (C) experiment 3. The slope of the curve provides inverse hydraulic resistance.

Figure 28: Measured values of flow rate at various pressure for leakage channel, and fits for chip 4-2 with setup leakage for 3 experiments; (A) experiment 1 (B) experiment 2 and (C) experiment 3. The slope of the curve provides inverse hydraulic resistance.

Similarly, Figure 28 represents a plot between flow rate at different pressure during the decay experiments for Chip 4-2. The slope of the curve provides inverse hydraulic resistance. Different

intercept values are because of compression of the trapped air bubbles inside the channel. Although we purge the channel before performing every experiment, there is always some air bubbles trapped inside the channel. Moreover, pressure drop in the system also accounts for the intercept in the curve. A summarized data representing hydraulic resistance is shown in Table 12. This resistance was calculated by doing inverse of the slope of curve from Figure 27 and Figure 28.

Table 12: Results from measurements of paired values of flow and pressure for chip 4-2 and chip 6-2 leakage.

Chip	Slope (mbar/ μ L/min)	Intercept (mbar)	Average Slope (mbar/ μ L/min)	Average Intercept (mbar)
4-2	27694	625.7	29040.67 (\pm 1168.72)	995.83 (\pm 349.50)
	29790	1041.6		
	29638	1320.2		
6-2	20669	2508	21324 (\pm 917.78)	2345.43 (\pm 403.03)

Figure 29: Theoretical values for pressure and flow rates for leakage channel dimension of $1.85 \mu\text{m} * 150 \mu\text{m} * 20 \text{mm}$ calculated using a standard equation.

Figure 29 show pressure and corresponding flow rates for leakage channel with the dimension of $1.85 \mu\text{m} * 150 \mu\text{m} * 20 \text{mm}$. Flow rate for various pressure were calculated using the equation below (Muzychka,2010):

$$\text{Flow} = \frac{\Delta P}{R}, R = \frac{1}{1 - (0.63h/w)} \frac{12\mu L}{h^3 w}$$

With:

- P the pressure
- R the hydraulic resistance
- μ the dynamic viscosity

L , h , w the length, height, and width of channel respectively.

As a rough estimate, hydraulic resistance for channel size of above dimension nearly matches our value. The tolerance provided for the height of leakage channel is ± 500 nm. Manufacturing defects such as etching depth, surface roughness might contribute to the pressure change especially for tiny channel height. Measuring exact dimension for the channel used could provide proper validation.

2.3.3.2.5. Discussion

We have tested 8 chips with main channels and 2 chips with leakage channel. For the main channels, tests were simple to conduct as the hydraulic resistance is quite small. However, number of issues were seen while working with leakage channels. Most common issues were related to leakage from the fittings. O-rings were used at almost all the fittings to prevent leakage. Because of high pressure involved in the testing, fittings were likely to leak. Similarly, air bubble present in the system were also common. Presence of these air bubbles contributed to slower development of pressure in the system especially while working with the leakage channels. Approach that we used for pressure measurement in syringe can be used for measuring high pressure. However, slippage of syringe was seen several times. So, two retort stands were used to hold the syringe tightly. Moreover, these stands were further clamped firmly on the working table. It is also recommended to measure tube diameter before using. MFMET provided tube size was slightly smaller than the one we have used. Also, the screws to fix the tubing to the glass chip were slipping.

It is suspected that the leakage channel in device 4-1 has a significant blockage in it because considerable time was spent trying to measure the leakage flow, but this was confounded by the repeated appearance of leakages at the chip/tubing interface and so measurements were instead performed on chip 4-2 (for which no chip/tubing were found using the same fittings and set-ups). Hence, a recommendation could be that different labs perform measurements on different chips since blockages of $2 \mu\text{m}$ channels are difficult to avoid. An appropriate protocol is needed for the cleaning of those tiny channels.

2.3.3.3. CETIAT

2.3.3.3.1. Instruments

The general view of the setup is shown on Figure 30. The flow generator is either a Nemesys syringe pump or an Elveflow pressure-driven pump, depending on the position of a manual valve. The water passes first through an Omega PXM409-001BGUSBH pressure sensor ranging from 0 to 1 barg. A valve can then send the flow through the chip or a bypass. The two paths converge downstream the chip before it goes through a quartz capillary. A camera tracks the meniscus of water to measure its displacement over time. Knowing the inner diameter of the capillary, and thus its cross section, enables to compute the flow rate.

Figure 30: Complete setup for the measurement of hydrodynamic resistance.

Figure 31: Detail of the syringe pump.

Figure 32: Detail of the chip under test.

CETIAT's optical measurement system consists of a JAI SP-12000M-CXP4-F camera (188 fps at 12MP), Qioptiq Optem FUSION Lens System 7:1 with a motorized zoom controller and a KL 2500 LED backlight for image acquisition, Quartz glass capillaries with inner diameters ranging from 250 μm to 1 mm to circulating water or water and oil, and 4 translation and 1 rotary stages. The principle is explained by Figure 33 and Figure 34. Camera calibration is realized using a calibrated Olympus OB-M transmitted light objective micrometer (Figure 35). A signal generator that is calibrated against an atomic clock is used for triggering the camera to start image acquisition. The nano-flow facility relies on a CETONI Nemesys syringe pump (using 1 mL to 10 μl syringes) to deliver flows ranging from 1 nL/min to 16 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$.

Figure 33: Setup to measure the flow rate downstream of the chip using an optical front track method.

Figure 34: Lens of the camera aiming at a capillary to track the meniscus.

Figure 35: Calibration target for the traceability of length when analysing the pictures from the camera.

2.3.3.3.2. Measurements

Due to difficulties to flow water through the leakage channels of the transfer standards, the hydrodynamic resistance was only evaluated in the main channels of chips 1-3 and 4-2. According to protocol of A2.4.3, the following configurations were used:

- 1E, which corresponds to channel #3 of design 1 on Figure 6,
- 4C, which corresponds to channel #2 of design 4 on Figure 6.

The measurements were done twice for each channel:

- 1) once with the syringe pump, which implies the setpoint is a flow rate,
- 2) then with the pressure-driven pump, which implies the setpoint is an inlet pressure.

As the setup at CETIAT did not allow for the measurement of differential pressure directly upstream and downstream of the chip, each measurement with the chip also had to be repeated through the bypass to compensate for the additional resistance of everything downstream the chip. Figure 36, Figure 37, Figure 38 and Figure 39 present the corresponding results, where:

- The blue datapoints “*main channel*” correspond to the hydrodynamic resistance of the channel AND everything downstream: $R_H(\text{all}) = R_H(\text{chip}) + R_H(\text{downstream})$. This is true

because the outlet of the circuit (at the end of the capillary with the front-track method) is at atmospheric pressure.

- The orange datapoints “bypass” correspond to hydrodynamic resistance of everything downstream only: R_H (downstream). The bypass is considered to have the same resistance as the tubing needed to connect the chip on the clamp connector shown on Figure 32.
- The dashed lines are the linear regressions of the respective datapoints. Their slopes correspond to the hydrodynamic resistance, thus the hydrodynamic resistance of the main channel alone is evaluated by subtracting the slope of “bypass” to the slope of “main channel”.

Finally, each measurement is repeated to get at least three iterations for each setpoint and each configuration. In total, about 140 measurements were performed to obtain the following data. The results are presented in Table 13.

Figure 36: Chip 1-3, flow generated by the syringe pump.

Figure 37: Chip 1-3, flow generated by the pressure-driven pump.

Figure 38: Chip 4-2, flow generated by the syringe pump.

Figure 39: Chip 4-2, flow generated by the pressure-driven pump.

Table 13: Hydrodynamic resistance results for each channel and flow generator.

Chip	Channel	Flow generator	$R_H(\text{all})$ bar.min/ μL	$R_H(\text{downstream})$ bar.min/ μL	$R_H(\text{chip})$ bar.min/ μL	$R_H(\text{chip})$ Pa.s/m^3
1-3	3	syringe	1.27 e-4	3.32 e-5	9.36 e-5	5.61 e11
1-3	3	pressure	1.24 e-4	2.77 e-5	9.62 e-5	5.77 e11
4-2	2	syringe	1.26 e-4	3.14 e-5	9.42 e-5	5.65 e11
4-2	2	pressure	1.30 e-4	2.66 e-5	1.04 e-4	6.21 e11

2.3.3.3.3. Discussion

The value for chip 4-2 with the pressure-driven pump appears less consistent than the other three values, while all main channels across the designs should be identical. It must be related to the repeatability issue that shows on Figure 39, where datapoints are more dispersed than they should be, although its origin is unclear and will be investigated in further works.

2.3.4. Flow rate

2.3.4.1. IPQ

IPQ used the gravimetric method to measure the flow rate of the glass chips using a nexus pump flow generator.

The gravimetric method at IPQ generates the flow with a syringe-pump a Nexus 3000 (figure 40), from Chemyx, using a 1 mL ILS glass syringe connected to polyethylene (PE) tube of 1,26 mm (0,05”) inner diameter which is immersed in the water in the weighing vessel on the balance (Mettler AX26, resolution 1 mg). In addition, this particular setup uses an evaporation trap to reduce evaporation, especially useful at low flow rates, and the connecting tube was inserted below the water surface inside the weighing vessel of the balance to avoid the drop impact effect. Thus, the mass flow rate is determined, and the volume flow rate can be calculated with the appropriate density of the liquid.

The time interval in which the mass is delivered is determined by a timing module to derive the mass flow rate. The data are collected from the balance every 250 ms during 60 min using a LabVIEW application. The flow is determined every 30 seconds.

The climatic conditions such as air temperature, relative humidity and pressure are determined to correct for buoyancy effects on the balance. The liquid measured in the beginning and at the end of the tests and used to convert the mass flow rate into a volumetric flow rate, considering the density of the liquid used.

At start of each measurement, it is required that the system on charge, and after that let it run for 10 minutes to stabilize.

Figure 40: Gravimetric method measurements at IPQ of the glass chips

For the flow measurements with the Nexus pump with and without chip, it was taken on consideration that the setup, the test time, the start position, and the syringe remained the same through all the measurements.

Unfortunately, it was not possible to measure the flow on the small channels due to the high pressure made by the pump.

Table 14: Gravimetric results of the glass chips with the Nexus Pump

Chip	Nominal Flow [mL/h]	Measured Flow [mL/h]	Error [%]	U [%]	Variation with and without chip [%]
Glass 1_1 Channel 1	0,01	0,0099	1,00	3,98	-0,92
	0,1	0,1014	-1,40	2,98	-1,49
	1	1,0124	-1,24	2,29	-0,88
Glass 1_2 Channel 2	0,01	0,0097	3,00	3,34	1,12
	0,1	0,104	-4,00	5,21	-4,09
	1	1,0047	-0,47	3,53	-0,11
Glass 2_1 Channel 2	0,01	0,0025	75,00	10,87	74,52
	0,1	0,103	-3,00	7,02	-3,09
	1	1,0047	-0,47	3,53	-0,11
Glass 2_1 Channel 3	0,01	0,0097	3,00	5,74	1,12
	0,1	0,1029	-2,90	6,65	-2,99
	1	1,002	-0,20	1,95	0,16
Glass 4_1 Channel 2	0,01	0,0108	-8,00	2,53	-10,09
	0,1	0,1024	-2,40	3,35	-2,49
	1	1,0004	-0,04	2,05	0,31
Glass 4_1 Channel 3	0,01	0,0092	8,00	4,80	6,22
	0,1	0,1019	-1,90	3,79	-1,99
	1	1,003	-0,30	1,93	0,06

It can be verified by the results that the use of the chip does not make influence in the set flow rate since the variation is within the measurement uncertainty.

2.3.4.2. Other laboratories

Information about the flow rate measurements is also available in the section about hydrodynamic resistance evaluation, see 2.3.3.

3. Polymer transfer standards

3.1. Fabrication and design of the transfer standards made of polymer

In microfluidics various thermoplastic polymers are used like Topas (COC – Cycloolefinic copolymer), Zeonor and Zeonex (Cycloolefinic polymer), PMMA (Polymethylmetacrylat), PC (Polycarbonate) or PS (Polystyrene). All these polymers are available in different grades with different e.g. thermal characteristics. Topas is one of the most prominent materials in microfluidics since its outstanding optical characteristics like low autofluorescence comparable to Borofloat glass and it is highly transparent in the visible spectrum, chemical resistance against ethanol or acetone and high barrier against water vapor. Furthermore, Topas grades are available that can be used at elevated temperature. The benefit of polymers is that due to the fabrication process of injection molding a real 3D structure can be realized allowing for the direct integration of e.g. fluidic interfaces.

The fabrication process used for the realization of the transfer standards made of polymers starts with the design generation, followed by the realization of a metal mold insert by ultra precision milling what is inserted in an injection molding tool. Mold insert and injection molding tool are placed in the injection molding machine where the inverse structure is replicated by injecting molten plastic in the injection molding tool. With cycle times usually of several ten seconds the microstructured part is generated. This part will be complemented in the afterwards assembly process in which a thin cover lid is mounted. The final process is an optical quality control (QC) after which the parts are safely package and labelled. The overall fabrication sequence is highlighted in the figure below.

Figure 40: Fabrication chain in polymer microfluidics and technologies used to realize the transfer standard in polymers (polymer chips)

Different from standard glass fabrication technologies as used for the transfer standard glass devices, the cross section of the microfluidic channel is trapezoid allowing a demolding of the hardened polymer from the mold insert and fluidic interfaces (here female Mini Luer Connectors) are integral part of the molded polymer from the mold insert and fluidic interfaces (here female Mini Luer Connectors) are integral part of the molded microfluidic chip allowing a direct integration of the fluidic interface male counterpart (here: male Tube Tuck Connectors).

Figure 41: Schematic view of the transfer standard polymer device

Figure 42: Top view of the transfer standard polymer device

Same as for the transfer standards in glass it was considered:

1. Compare the leakage rate measurement with air (preferred industrial test method) with liquid leakage rate (in microfluidic application)
2. Enable very low flows for flow rate measurements

Therefore, several very small channels partially of different length (here called leakage channels) with common inlet port and separate outlet ports should be considered. One should be able to close or open such ports individually.

The leakage channel allows for a liquid flow rate of 10 nl/min minimum with an inlet pressure of 100 mbar to 2 bar. The set of 8 transfer standards designs allows to test separately simple microfluidic geometries and their combinations, representing typical fluidic configurations encountered by microfluidic end users.

The cross section of the leakage channel and their length will define the resistance within the measurement.

The channel with the largest diameter in the leakage channel (100 μm) will serve as reference.

Table 15: Technical specification for the transfer standards made of polymers.

Description of the parameter	Value	Tolerance	Comment
Material molded part	COC	NA	/
Thickness without fluidic interfaces	1.5 mm	± 0.025mm	/
Depth main channels:	200 µm	± 1.0 µm	
Width main channels bottom:	466 µm	± 1.5 µm	
Width main channels top:	502 µm	± 2.5 µm	
Leakage channel 1			
Width bottom	82,5 µm	± 1 µm	
Width top	100 µm	± 2 µm	
Depth	100 µm	± 1 µm	
Length	40.1 mm	± 100 µm	
Leakage channel 2			
Width bottom	41.25 µm	± 1 µm	
Width top	50 µm	± 2 µm	
Depth	50 µm	± 1 µm	
Length	40.1 mm	± 100 µm	
Leakage channel 3			
Width bottom	16.5 µm	± 1 µm	
Width top	20 µm	± 2 µm	
Depth	20 µm	± 1 µm	
Length	40.1 mm	± 100 µm	
Leakage channel 4			
Width bottom	8.25 µm	± 1 µm	
Width top	10 µm	± 2 µm	
Depth	10 µm	± 1 µm	
Length	40.1 mm	± 100 µm	
Leakage channel 5			
Width bottom	41.25 µm	± 1 µm	
Width top	50 µm	± 2 µm	
Depth	50 µm	± 1 µm	
Length	20.1mm	± 100 µm	
Leakage channel 6			
Width bottom	16.5 µm	± 1 µm	
Width top	20 µm	± 2 µm	
Depth	20 µm	± 1 µm	
Length	20.1mm	± 100 µm	
Leakage channel 7			
Width bottom	8.25 µm	± 1 µm	
Width top	10 µm	± 2 µm	
Depth	10 µm	± 1 µm	
Length	20.1 mm	± 100 µm	
Leakage channel 8			
Width bottom	4.1 µm	± 1 µm	
Width top	5 µm	± 2 µm	
Depth	5 µm	± 1 µm	
Length	20.1 mm	± 100 µm	
Through holes	∅0.5 mm	± 0.05mm	In through holes flash might occur resulting in up to +100 µm
Thickness of thin cover lid	140 µm	± 10 µm	/

3.2. Fabrication and design of the fluidic interfaces for the transfer standards made of polymer: Male Mini Luer Tube Tuck Connectors

For the evaluation of the transfer standard polymer device Male Mini Luer Tube Tuck Connectors are foreseen to be used with respective tubes as shown in Figure 43 and in the overall assembly in Figure 44.

Figure 43: Fluidic interfaces (Male Mini Luer Tube Tuck Connector) used with the transfer standard polymer device

Figure 44: Transfer standard device polymer with Male Tube Tuck Connectors

3.3. Evaluation kit and use: transfer standards made of polymer and Male Mini Luer Tube Tuck Connectors

Allowing for an easy handling of the transfer standards and having the influencing elements of the set-up (transfer standard device, fluidic interface and connecting tube) at hand an evaluation kit was compiled.

For the use of the transfer standards made of polymers needs to be considered:

1. Topas (COC) is sensitive to fats, fatty acids or mineral oils. Handling with gloves is therefore recommended.
2. After either handling with naked hands over a while (days) or over longer use, the material shows cracks and the transfer standard made of polymers should be discarded.
3. After use with water, the transfer standard can be dried by air blow and afterwards dried in an oven at 40 °C or at room temperature

Table 16: Evaluation kit transfer standard made of polymers available at microfluidic ChipShop

Nr.	Component	Quantity in kit
1	Handling frame with high skirt	2
2	Transfer standard polymer: Microfluidic chip 1575	10
3	Mini Luer Tube Tuck connectors for 1/32 tubing, fluidic 997, Material: TPE, green	4 units (10 parts each)
4	Micro tubes PTFE, ID: 0.5 mm, OD: 1.0 mm	1 m
5	Male Mini Luer plugs - Low vol. displ., TPE green	4 units (10 parts each)

Figure 45: Pictures of components of the evaluation kit transfer standard made of polymers

3.4. Results of the experiments conducted in A2.4.3

The results of the measurements performed with the polymer transfer standards are presented in the following sub-sections. See also section 4 about the challenges encountered during these measurements.

3.4.1. Dimensions

Dimensional measurements were performed by LNE, CEA and University of Glasgow on the polymer transfer standards. The results are however not yet available for sharing to the day of the present report. A paper entitled “Comparison of measurement protocols for internal channels of transparent microfluidic devices” by Joris Kaal (CEA), Nicolas Feltin (LNE), Huabing Yin (University of Glasgow) *et al.* is ready for submission and will be published after the completion of MFMET.

3.4.2. Volume and hydrodynamic resistance

Due to lack of time during the experiments, these results are missing to the day of the present report but work on this topic is planned to continue under the EURAMET Pilot Study 1613 (see section 4 about the feedback for more information).

3.4.3. Flow rate

3.4.3.1. IPQ

To achieve consistent results, the setup was made with a Elvexys flow pressure pump as represented on Figure 46. Initially the pump is connected to a pressure source, and then positioned higher than the reservoir to prevent backflow, the reservoir is filled with the testing liquid which will travel through the tube and pass through the ElveFlow sensor. The sensor is positioned slightly above the microchip,

which is at the same high as the trash. Using the ElveFlow software it is possible choose the pretended flow to measure, visualising graphically on the software, and after the measurement can save the results to further analysis.

It is recommended to get the system on charge before starting the measurements, after it being on charge let the pump run itself for 10 minutes to stabilize, and then start the measurement. After finishing the first measurement, set the new flow, and let it work for about 5 minutes to stabilize and then start the measurement, this step is recommended for each measurement.

Figure 46: Gravimetric setup using the pressure pump and polymer chips.

The results are presented in Table 17.

Table 17: Flow rate measurements by IPQ with the polymer transfer standards.

Chip (+ flow generator)	Nominal Flow [mL/h]	Measured Flow [mL/h]	Error [%]	U (%)	Variation with and without chip [%]
Channel 5 big (ElveFlow)	0,025	0,0265	-6,00	1,92	0,75
	0,1	0,1078	-7,80	0,79	-1,32
	0,4	0,5215	-30,38	3,24	1,40
Channel 5 small (ElveFlow)	0,025	0,0237	5,20	4,64	11,24
	0,1	0,1036	-3,60	4,34	2,63
	0,4	0,5398	-34,95	2,76	-2,06
Channel 8 big (ElveFlow)	0,025	0,024	4,00	1,80	10,11
	0,1	0,1011	-1,10	3,51	4,98
	0,4	0,513	-28,25	3,19	3,01
Channel 8 big (Nexus)	0,025	0,021	16,00	5,56	18,29
	0,1	0,0987	1,30	3,25	1,21
	0,4	0,39	2,50	3,45	2,13
Channel 5 big (Nexus)	0,025	0,0253	-1,20	13,62	1,56
	0,1	0,0985	1,50	5,03	1,41
	0,4	0,3877	3,08	2,83	2,71

In this case two different flow generators were used, the Nexus syringe pump and a pressure pump. It was possible to test the small flow channel with the pressure pumps. Also, the uncertainties are smaller when using the pressure pump. The variation obtained with and without the chip are in general lower than the uncertainty and this means the chip has no effect in the set flow rate, but some significant differences were observed at very small flow rate.

3.4.3.2. FDA

FDA completed testing on two of the leakage designs of polymer chips and developed an analytical approach to calculate leakage through chips. The variability in leakage across multiple channels was minimal. Additionally, the relative error of the analytical model was < 10 %, demonstrating good agreement with experimental findings.

The leakage for Design #1 varied from 1.97 - 2.03 % across 3 chips. The corresponding leakage for Design #5 varied from 0.25 – 0.28 %. The run-to-run variability for each chip was also small (1.93-1.97 %).

The relative error of the analytical method compared to the experimental results was about 5 %.

The inlet and outlet tubing contributes significantly towards the resistivity of the set up, and hence for interlaboratory comparisons it would be meaningful to compare leakage after harmonizing the internal dimensions and length of all the tubing.

Figure 47: Geometry of Polymer Microchip Design #5 tested by FDA.

Figure 48: Internal dimensions and leakage % for design 1 (100 x 100 μm) of 3 different chips (all triplicates)

Figure 49: Internal dimensions and leakage % for design 5 (50 x 50 μm) of 3 different chips (all triplicates)

4. Feedback on the challenges encountered during A2.4.3

Various difficulties were encountered during the comparison, thus preventing the project to fully carry out the experiments and analysis that were initially planned for A2.4.3.

4.1. Project dependencies

A few partners were impacted by changes of personnel during the project, both affecting the measurements and the management. In particular, the WP2 leader was replaced in July 2023, just when activity A2.4.3 started.

TUBITAK UME is not mentioned in the results above although they participated in the experiments. Various difficulties prevented them from getting measurements during the time they had the glass transfer standards. As delays had already accumulated before their turn, it was decided to reschedule their experiments at the end of the test matrix. However, further delays with the next partners prevented the chips to be sent back to TUBITAK UME before the end of MFMET.

4.2. Time schedule

Transfer standards were only available for testing from early October 2023, and the clamp connector needed for flow measurements was only delivered in late October 2023

The test matrix of A2.4.3 was too ambitious for the time available.

- Only two weeks were allocated per partner, without consideration for the time needed for travel and sometimes customs. With 8 international partners and New Year's holidays during the period, it would have finished in late February 2024 at best, only three months before the end of the project.
- The time needed for each test was underestimated, even without technical difficulties. Even though the number of repetitions required to evaluate the reproducibility of the manufacturing processes and the consistency of the measurements was anticipated, it was difficult to guess the time needed to get a single datapoint. The method is different in each laboratory, and some quantities were new to some partners, which required adapting their usual setup.

4.3. Technical challenges

For measurements of flow and hydrodynamic resistance, difficulties were found by all partners in driving and measuring flow through the leakage channels of the glass chips. This might be caused by the very small size of the leakage channels ($150\ \mu\text{m} \times 2\ \mu\text{m}$) or partial to total blockage of the channels by small particles. Checking the chips with air at least confirmed the leakage channels were not totally blocked, and water was even observed flowing through for some chips (Figure 50). However, at least for the glass chip 1-1, the flow within the leakage channel was seen disturbed by small particles (Figure 51). This subject would deserve to be investigated in future works and protocols, and several partners

already possess the tools to observe the behaviour of flows in such microchannels. The surface state inside the leakage channels might also play a more predominant role than inside the main channels.

Figure 50: Water is seen flowing from the main channel (left) through the leakage channel (horizontal) of chip 1-3, during a check for blockage at CETIAT.

Figure 51: Water (in white) flowing from right to left through the leakage channel of glass chip 1-1.

When characterizing hydrodynamic resistance of small channels that are associated with similarly high pressure and small volumetric flow, it may be very worth to consider a procedure like the one proposed by the University of Glasgow. Here the fluidic path upstream of the leakage channel was

pressurised and then the pump was stopped, allowing a slowly decaying pressure and flow through the leakage channel. For very small channels, such a decay might reach conditions much closer to steady state laminar flow than a flow influenced by a pump. Such a protocol could also improve the efficiency of the plan of experiments, as it might allow for quicker measurements. It would however require an accurate description of the protocol and a test setup capable of recording the pressure and flow rate synchronously.

4.4. Future works

Based on the same protocol from A2.4.3, the EURAMET pilot study 1613 was initiated [8]. This study is open to a wider range of participants and can last outside of the scope of FMET, which will give more time for obtaining and analysing the results that are missing from this report. The results may later serve for submitting new CMCs by the partners, thus contributing to a research environment where traceability in flow-related quantities for microfluidics is easier to achieve.

An abstract has been submitted for presenting these results at CIM2025, the next international metrology congress. The paper is entitled “Characterisation of microfluidic transfer standards: results and challenges” and it will also present additional analysis that could not be included in the present report.

5. References

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